

Hierarchical Condition Tree on Trattamento Report

Experiment : Tutti VS Tutti
Active entity list : All Entities

Condition dataset colors Condition

[6PP]	[76A]	[BIO+6PP]	[BIO+76A]	[BIO+T22+76A]
[BIO+T22]	[BIO]	[CTRL]	[T22+76A]	[T22]

Condition dataset colors Trattamento

6PP	76A	BIO	BIO+6PP	BIO+76A
BIO+T22	BIO+T22+76A	CTRL	T22	T22+76A

Entity color by FC ([6PP] vs [CTRL])

Description

Created from Advanced Analysis operation: Clustering:

Entity List: Fold change ≥ 2.0

Interpretation: Trattamento

Experiment: Tutti VS Tutti

Clustering Algorithm: Hierarchical

Clustered By: Normalized intensity values

Clustered On: Conditions

Similarity Measure: Euclidean

Linkage Rule: Wards

Cluster Within Conditions: No

Compound	[T22+76A]	[BIO+T22]	[T22]	[BIO]	[BIO+T22+76A]	[6PP]	[76A]	[CTRL]	[BIO+6PP]	[BIO+76A]
> limit	3.3448431	2.453521	2.0818315	2.5982106	2.4753175	1.9365934	1.6371324	-19.718834	1.8312106	2.2656622
C23 H14 N4	2.806929	2.4304237	2.299166	2.49447	2.4117515	3.0124674	2.10622	3.3246088	2.0349185	2.3685093
C46 H92 N2	-19.832893	0.61749625	-0.10796229	0.9240449	0.5455871	-19.404182	-0.49772814	0.24931294	0.006888283	0.349635
> limit nullnull	1.921441	2.4952714	2.3218114	2.1510944	2.1501234	2.5310056	-0.7303467	-1.1130674	1.8375323	2.4592505
C16 H42 N9	-19.832893	2.0147002	1.6158161	2.3378181	2.0673041	1.4814886	1.3915168	1.8457563	0.9958074	1.9614732
Apigenin-7-O-	1.5033057	1.4602767	1.7366958	-1.7909541	-1.8573903	1.7936137	1.503795	1.7304397	1.3687036	1.651465
Cirsimaritin	-19.832893	1.2916601	1.4347414	1.5231508	1.4452589	1.4168752	-19.73876	-19.718834	-1.0464625	-19.789707
C21 H22 N6	0.67297554	0.75725895	0.60777324	0.5377418	0.63836884	-1.1554686	-0.45939064	-1.0072798	-1.2987978	-0.88990784
Ferulic acid	-19.832893	0.5660142	0.5247733	0.7227817	0.5547706	0.56400895	0.39242533	0.38488558	-19.887903	-19.789707
Apigenin-7-O-	-0.20754136	0.19268799	0.19957373	1.3508478	1.2972881	-0.23317549	0.029397752	0.19091395	-0.23055945	0.09013727
C18 H31 O8	-19.832893	0.18943278	0.14909087	-0.10250621	-0.09999529	-0.021526761	-0.014366574	0.20449342	-0.88099164	-0.7008779
C14 H14 O9	-19.832893	0.07966105	0.038760714	0.29938444	0.061661825	0.1455201	-0.04279518	-0.13326137	-19.887903	-19.789707
Medioresinol	-19.832893	-6.3885846	0.3421633	0.31183708	0.29124302	-19.404182	-19.73876	-19.718834	-19.887903	-19.789707
Tricetin 3'-me	-19.832893	-19.726458	-19.74753	-0.27462196	-19.832815	-19.404182	-19.73876	-19.718834	-19.887903	-19.789707
Luteolin-3-O-	-19.832893	-10.961895	-19.74753	0.13141972	-19.832815	-19.404182	-19.73876	-19.718834	-19.887903	-19.789707
C22 H18 O13	-0.24527614	-0.49198425	-0.5421829	-0.015630297	-0.41638905	-19.404182	-0.9022634	-0.1719746	-19.887903	-19.789707
Lanceolitol B1	-0.24758318	0.40550315	0.17451371	0.2622545	0.38179758	0.55737853	0.31177944	-6.503918	0.47551027	0.310297
C24 H34 N4	-19.832893	0.19168387	-1.1319938	0.048547532	0.18270747	0.5916947	0.3152324	-1.8221122	0.26507527	-0.9790376
C18 H24 N7	-19.832893	-0.36172634	-0.6159842	-0.3898129	-0.3126242	-19.404182	-19.73876	-19.718834	-19.887903	-19.789707
C24 H45 N2	-0.3272718	-1.0883719	-1.410646	-0.91712123	-1.0447458	-19.404182	-19.73876	-1.2250671	-1.4388881	-1.0443339
Medioresinol	0.1521598	-6.816313	-0.11129803	-0.2543848	-0.011365890	0.5599439	0.49784598	0.31076303	0.3466055	0.43803766
438.1653@4.	-19.832893	-6.7271557	-0.04559665	-0.1613352	0.009925206	-19.404182	-19.73876	-19.718834	-19.887903	-19.789707
C23 H32 O2	-19.832893	-13.170513	-6.7689	-7.25984	-19.832815	-19.404182	-19.73876	-7.505228	-19.887903	-19.789707
Phenylacetic	-19.832893	-19.726458	-19.74753	-0.71351963	-0.4636366	-0.4850146	-19.73876	-0.41833624	-19.887903	-19.789707
C23 H38 N9	-0.90930474	-19.726458	-19.74753	-0.21233092	-0.41741118	-0.54021686	-0.5022962	-0.31897354	-0.7611641	-0.7236207
Lupinisoflavo	-0.21267043	-7.0906577	-0.17627399	-0.80110466	-0.20688397	0.31848186	0.17838733	0.12552197	0.2692053	0.40560383
Rosmarinic a	1.3393095	-19.726458	0.35674202	0.71885	0.62063134	0.4970714	0.09384452	-19.718834	0.3246693	-1.487103
C34 H18 N14	-0.6513379	-19.726458	-19.74753	-1.1517473	-19.832815	-19.404182	-19.73876	-19.718834	-19.887903	-19.789707
Apigenin-7-O-	-19.832893	-19.726458	-19.74753	0.1655905	0.15413305	-2.8438125	-19.73876	-19.718834	-19.887903	-19.789707
> limit nullnull	-0.8652988	-1.7678564	-2.221985	-1.5011204	-1.7951093	-19.404182	-19.73876	-19.718834	-2.2699254	-2.169306
> limit nullnull	-0.28811878	-2.2270393	-3.0932114	-2.285642	-2.1488984	-3.1358843	-19.73876	-19.718834	-2.9308226	-1.9997202
C17 H24 N6	-0.67368823	-0.39403725	-2.1880388	-0.82856244	-0.2910188	-0.6602819	-3.6284795	-0.32891804	-0.9927171	-0.30697885
C13 H18 N6	-19.832893	-19.726458	-19.74753	-0.8005551	-19.832815	-19.404182	-19.73876	-19.718834	-19.887903	-19.789707
C32 H50 N7	-0.8337097	-19.726458	-0.7128612	-0.5664508	-0.79093194	-0.56969327	-0.36990377	-19.718834	-19.887903	-19.789707
C23 H38 O8	-1.7026803	-1.0083646	0.12963253	-0.9871078	-1.0121083	-0.47541407	-0.99256283	0.8007054	-1.048815	-1.0332532
C17 H24 O9	-1.2323543	-1.2167172	-1.1768502	-1.2897601	-19.832815	-0.7424274	-1.0180488	-19.718834	-19.887903	-19.789707
C26 H20 N O	-19.832893	-19.726458	-1.1165553	-1.157992	-1.3440176	-0.8454628	-0.77306813	-19.718834	-1.5885745	-19.789707
C18 H24 N7	-19.832893	-7.418032	-19.74753	-1.1107466	-0.9017296	-0.39224836	-0.38568074	-19.718834	-0.34099197	-0.4289678
C17 H24 N7	-19.832893	-0.69456947	-0.6558541	-0.74963	-0.81807643	-0.40758365	-0.48671192	-0.683776	-0.85732776	-0.58385235
Cirsimaritin n	1.7404084	-1.9626187	-1.72548	-1.5547698	-19.832815	-1.7363516	1.0677847	1.4522684	-1.9344913	1.3223945
C5 H4 N4	-19.832893	-0.70393604	-1.0235977	-0.71499103	-0.61879605	-0.56457245	-0.94563633	-3.061072	-0.7597794	-1.0765659
C13 H32 N16	-19.832893	-0.7775328	-19.74753	-0.9330796	-0.8373574	-0.36638832	-0.7727801	-0.70587456	-0.7166165	-0.6905842
C32 H44 N13	-19.832893	-19.726458	-1.5947399	-1.5591022	-19.832815	-1.506222	-1.0746435	-19.718834	-19.887903	-1.4139705
C12 H11 N9	-1.1381679	-19.726458	-19.74753	-3.2951012	-19.832815	-19.404182	-19.73876	-19.718834	-19.887903	-19.789707
1,8-Cineole	-19.832893	-1.751955	-1.4596857	-1.6328866	-19.832815	-19.404182	-19.73876	-1.9273112	-1.8335961	-1.8155187
> limit nullnull	-1.4331697	-2.0398643	-2.4388812	-2.1236129	-1.6178303	-19.404182	-2.6558008	-1.7107056	-2.1852942	-1.4766257
C36 H32 O16	-1.8286614	-2.6208854	-19.74753	-3.3993442	-19.832815	-2.6775336	-19.73876	-19.718834	-1.7813367	-19.789707

Compound	[T22+76A]	[BIO+T22]	[T22]	[BIO]	[BIO+T22+76A]	[6PP]	[76A]	[CTRL]	[BIO+6PP]	[BIO+76A]
C20 H36 O12	-1.4159355	-1.3277419	-19.74753	-1.4066849	-1.6110177	-1.1696807	-1.3849025	-1.3730788	-19.887903	-1.5282887
C17 H21 N8	-19.832893	-19.726458	-1.4294248	-1.4745307	-1.6255308	-1.3539113	-1.4961638	-1.291142	-19.887903	-1.52128
C34 H36 N4	-2.7151392	-19.726458	-2.7637877	-2.6545055	-3.1621344	-2.2047825	-2.7918236	-2.4274244	-3.1587343	-19.789707
C33 H40 O17	-19.832893	-19.726458	-2.1993334	-2.039048	-19.832815	-2.2933874	-2.5557754	-19.718834	-19.887903	-19.789707
2'-Hydroxyisol	-19.832893	-0.92271	-3.0252736	-19.665823	-19.832815	-2.7318878	0.7175263	0.77759445	0.7527881	0.90814567
C37 H40 N4	-19.832893	-19.726458	-19.74753	-19.665823	-19.832815	-19.404182	-19.73876	1.9248854	1.6132017	-19.789707
Ferulic acid n	0.974653	-19.726458	-19.74753	-19.665823	-19.832815	-19.404182	-19.73876	-19.718834	-0.07628229	0.40208945
<none> nulln	0.19853741	-0.56216073	-0.8635985	-19.665823	-0.5027945	-0.9447539	-1.0645101	-0.7157082	-0.8147227	-0.48573345
Luteolin-3-O-	-19.832893	-19.726458	-19.74753	-19.665823	-19.832815	-19.404182	-19.73876	-19.718834	0.88563645	1.0513098
> limit nullnull	-19.832893	-19.726458	-19.74753	-19.665823	-19.832815	-19.404182	-19.73876	-19.718834	0.231095	-19.789707
Phenylacetic	-0.21488445	-19.726458	-19.74753	-19.665823	-19.832815	-19.404182	-19.73876	-19.718834	-0.43412992	-0.44763482
Rotundic acid	-19.832893	-19.726458	-19.74753	-19.665823	-0.61986816	-19.404182	-19.73876	-6.688359	-0.056236267	-19.789707
> limit nullnull	-19.832893	-19.726458	-19.74753	-19.665823	-19.832815	-19.404182	-1.6120319	-1.8029308	-0.4307287	-1.4620471
C16 H29 N3	-0.038157992	-19.726458	-19.74753	-19.665823	-19.832815	-19.404182	-19.73876	-19.718834	-1.0720493	-1.041472
Foliasalaciosi	-0.6430649	-0.7514496	-0.88826966	-19.665823	-0.32943684	-0.54327667	-0.84107906	-0.56691104	-0.8565178	-0.5411589
Foliasalaciosi	-0.28565067	-0.3704745	-0.3421455	-19.665823	-19.832815	-0.10909632	-0.24252446	-0.1943745	-0.1957264	0.009456634
C31 H54 N7	-19.832893	-19.726458	-1.4210417	-19.665823	-19.832815	-1.4207139	-1.4288497	-1.4946036	-1.4339226	-1.5289735
C21 H25 N2	-19.832893	-1.522309	-19.74753	-19.665823	-19.832815	-19.404182	-19.73876	-19.718834	-1.6726358	-19.789707
> limit nullnull	-19.832893	-1.0583526	-1.092637	-19.665823	-1.0666845	-19.404182	-0.73811656	-0.96213555	-1.0550265	-0.84612274
C29 H48 N9	-19.832893	-19.726458	-19.74753	-19.665823	-19.832815	-0.7256836	-1.109009	-1.1041052	-1.0935874	-19.789707
C39 H78 O2	-1.7327199	-1.8551755	-19.74753	-19.665823	-1.6051524	-19.404182	-19.73876	-19.718834	-2.0352337	-1.7202878
C18 H29 N O	-19.832893	-19.726458	-19.74753	-19.665823	-19.832815	-19.404182	-19.73876	-19.718834	-2.209421	-19.789707
C42 H90 N3	-19.832893	-19.726458	-19.74753	-19.665823	-19.832815	-19.404182	-19.73876	-19.718834	-2.169529	-19.789707
Apigenin-7-O-	-1.6929929	-19.726458	-1.8448832	-19.665823	-19.832815	-1.4655658	-1.6661156	-1.6917068	-1.5986044	-1.403091
C21 H30 N O	-19.832893	-19.726458	-19.74753	-19.665823	-19.832815	-19.404182	-19.73876	-19.718834	-2.1026566	-19.789707
C46 H92 N2	2.3685565	-19.726458	-19.74753	-19.665823	-19.832815	-19.404182	-19.73876	-19.718834	-19.887903	-19.789707
<none> nulln	0.51388866	-19.726458	-19.74753	-19.665823	-19.832815	-19.404182	-19.73876	-19.718834	-19.887903	-19.789707
C27 H24 O13	1.1273335	-19.726458	-19.74753	-19.665823	-19.832815	-19.404182	-19.73876	-19.718834	-19.887903	-19.789707
Rosmarinic a	-1.3003527	-19.726458	-1.1660514	-19.665823	-1.1427419	-0.63462913	-19.73876	-19.718834	-19.887903	-19.789707
C14 H14 O9	0.55682075	-19.726458	-19.74753	-19.665823	-19.832815	-19.404182	-19.73876	-19.718834	-19.887903	-0.13420762
7-Hydroxycou	-0.85172296	-19.726458	-19.74753	-19.665823	-19.832815	-1.4068773	-19.73876	-19.718834	-19.887903	-19.789707
Cirsimaritin n	-1.2925402	-19.726458	-19.74753	-19.665823	-19.832815	-19.404182	-19.73876	-19.718834	-19.887903	-19.789707
Caffeic acid n	1.4838725	-19.726458	-19.74753	-19.665823	-19.832815	-19.404182	-19.73876	-19.718834	-19.887903	-19.789707
7-Hydroxycou	-1.6666658	-19.726458	-19.74753	-19.665823	-19.832815	-19.404182	-19.73876	-19.718834	-19.887903	-19.789707
Medioresinol	-0.10375256	-19.726458	-19.74753	-19.665823	-19.832815	-19.404182	0.048688676	-0.1121858	-19.887903	-19.789707
C33 H22 N7	-1.627576	-19.726458	-19.74753	-19.665823	-19.832815	-19.404182	-19.73876	-19.718834	-19.887903	-19.789707
C13 H10 O8	-0.6450511	-0.95431924	-19.74753	-19.665823	-19.832815	-19.404182	-19.73876	-0.94754493	-19.887903	-1.025742
Caffeic acid n	-0.66645473	-19.726458	-19.74753	-19.665823	-19.832815	-19.404182	-19.73876	-19.718834	-19.887903	-19.789707
4-Hydroxyben	-19.832893	-19.726458	-19.74753	-19.665823	-19.832815	-19.404182	-19.73876	-19.718834	-19.887903	0.6686249
C23 H38 O8	-19.832893	-19.726458	-1.1523546	-19.665823	-19.832815	-19.404182	-19.73876	-19.718834	-19.887903	0.32063782
C23 H18 N7	-19.832893	-19.726458	-19.74753	-19.665823	-19.832815	-19.404182	-19.73876	-19.718834	-19.887903	0.047996733
Isocitric acid	-19.832893	-19.726458	-0.66440624	-19.665823	-19.832815	-6.7197223	-19.73876	-19.718834	-19.887903	-7.2063828
> limit nullnull	-19.832893	-1.2203013	-1.3385097	-19.665823	-19.832815	-19.404182	-19.73876	-19.718834	-19.887903	-1.3638797
C16 H26 N3	-19.832893	-19.726458	-19.74753	-19.665823	-19.832815	-1.5097114	-1.7584987	-19.718834	-19.887903	-1.6425005
C31 H34 N7	-19.832893	-2.119058	-19.74753	-19.665823	-19.832815	-19.404182	-2.1817012	-1.7762299	-19.887903	-2.0630016
438.1646@3.	-19.832893	-19.726458	-19.74753	-19.665823	-19.832815	0.015142017	-19.73876	-19.718834	-19.887903	-19.789707
C18 H32 O5	-19.832893	-19.726458	-19.74753	-19.665823	-19.832815	-1.2297475	-1.319418	-1.4344401	-19.887903	-19.789707

Compound	[T22+76A]	[BIO+T22]	[T22]	[BIO]	[BIO+T22+76 A]	[6PP]	[76A]	[CTRL]	[BIO+6PP]	[BIO+76A]
C22 H32 N7	-19.832893	-19.726458	-19.74753	-19.665823	-0.9139788	-1.3796635	-19.73876	-0.9236344	-19.887903	-19.789707
C18 H21 N8	-19.832893	-19.726458	-19.74753	-19.665823	-19.832815	-1.3964217	-19.73876	-19.718834	-19.887903	-19.789707
> limit nullnull	-19.832893	-19.726458	-19.74753	-19.665823	-19.832815	-19.404182	2.7039068	2.4703653	-19.887903	-19.789707
C24 H20 N21	-19.832893	-19.726458	-19.74753	-19.665823	-19.832815	-19.404182	-1.7215972	-19.718834	-19.887903	-19.789707
Foliasalaciosi	-19.832893	-19.726458	-19.74753	-19.665823	-0.85142815	-19.404182	-19.73876	-19.718834	-19.887903	-19.789707

Mass	Retention Time	Frequency	normalized_6PP_R1_1: Log2	normalized_6PP_R1_2: Log2	normalized_6PP_R1_3: Log2	normalized_6PP_R2_1: Log2	normalized_6PP_R2_2: Log2	normalized_6PP_R2_3: Log2	normalized_6PP_R3_1: Log2	normalized_6PP_R3_2: Log2
948.1609	4.8090005	81	0.49533463	0.5185909	0.5302067	2.5179596	2.4637413	2.422449	2.7409058	2.8332787
474.0798	4.8095016	90	2.162634	2.1537857	2.1410236	3.3576756	3.3024502	3.2675304	3.4992485	3.5833302
720.7122	5.0686274	72	-19.406227	-19.407225	-19.39549	-19.347189	-19.416286	-19.453854	-19.512691	-19.378508
804.3788	5.6625032	90	2.489355	2.46698	2.4718056	2.590294	2.5153332	2.4937248	2.5229797	2.5928516
360.3564	5.0576677	81	-0.0993309	-0.35679817	-0.17927742	2.5517406	2.4952145	2.4758549	2.0888443	2.2014618
432.1993	4.476197	90	1.889225	1.8430843	1.9431343	1.4641972	1.428585	1.4312878	1.9972038	1.977169
314.079	5.7194347	53	0.74191666	0.6499939	0.68699265	1.8669453	1.6658173	1.7211037	1.6699142	1.8590641
422.1707	4.5474987	90	-0.860157	-1.1885853	-0.6032772	-1.1204567	-1.2682076	-1.1969547	-1.4412231	-1.3073902
194.0577	4.3545704	63	0.11456108	0.13457108	0.28608513	0.39774323	0.22871971	0.032110214	1.0384083	1.3802185
432.1991	4.5856	90	-0.15736389	-0.039215088	-0.008584976	-0.31646538	-0.5424366	-0.32881355	-0.29673195	-0.29011726
407.1731	4.3812246	81	-0.012390137	-0.012998581	-0.04932022	0.030210495	0.03898239	0.03199005	-0.0643177	-0.09214401
326.0634	4.3545704	63	-0.3012886	-0.29122353	-0.13840866	-0.026420593	-0.20134354	-0.40564156	0.65055656	0.9807167
448.1931	4.369249	36	-19.406227	-19.407225	-19.39549	-19.347189	-19.416286	-19.453854	-19.512691	-19.378508
492.0885	4.4389997	9	-19.406227	-19.407225	-19.39549	-19.347189	-19.416286	-19.453854	-19.512691	-19.378508
448.1219	3.8884993	18	-19.406227	-19.407225	-19.39549	-19.347189	-19.416286	-19.453854	-19.512691	-19.378508
490.074	4.7285714	63	-19.406227	-19.407225	-19.39549	-19.347189	-19.416286	-19.453854	-19.512691	-19.378508
584.3019	6.2631993	90	0.83748245	0.8409958	0.8141804	0.64305496	0.50849533	0.5052891	0.22629738	0.28617477
442.2564	5.773555	81	0.98062134	0.9374218	0.96551704	0.56778336	0.48158073	0.41747475	0.25102615	0.35282135
402.1882	4.37025	36	-19.406227	-19.407225	-19.39549	-19.347189	-19.416286	-19.453854	-19.512691	-19.378508
361.3596	5.062622	72	-19.406227	-19.407225	-19.39549	-19.347189	-19.416286	-19.453854	-19.512691	-19.378508
448.1945	4.1811013	90	0.6048298	0.7145462	0.58301926	0.5512028	0.50839806	0.55750465	0.42606735	0.5383854
438.1653	4.3697495	36	-19.406227	-19.407225	-19.39549	-19.347189	-19.416286	-19.453854	-19.512691	-19.378508
340.2409	8.467999	36	-19.406227	-19.407225	-19.39549	-19.347189	-19.416286	-19.453854	-19.512691	-19.378508
136.0518	4.3357515	36	-0.89463234	-0.94361305	-1.02845	-0.011638641	0.029081345	0.120550156	-0.45230484	-0.6169605
552.2896	6.979252	72	-0.22653198	-0.39977837	-0.39779282	-0.61909485	-1.0860481	-0.9103508	-0.24437332	-0.5658283
438.1652	4.1816964	90	0.6338196	0.6328907	0.46136284	0.20104599	0.22916031	0.3896103	0.27424812	0.056446075
360.0843	5.070247	72	-0.37665367	-0.36180496	-0.4754696	1.5130196	1.195919	1.1441803	0.5618572	0.5124035
718.1535	5.146499	18	-19.406227	-19.407225	-19.39549	-19.347189	-19.416286	-19.453854	-19.512691	-19.378508
432.1993	4.7140007	27	-3.6332426	-3.7572947	-2.6898727	-2.843954	-3.0017014	-2.6256924	-2.9155407	-1.8750153
848.1801	5.101713	63	-19.406227	-19.407225	-19.39549	-19.347189	-19.416286	-19.453854	-19.512691	-19.378508
848.8198	5.0805035	72	-5.466648	-5.342313	-5.7520847	-2.4240932	-2.0740128	-1.8174915	-1.5701828	-1.7117348
424.1718	4.511198	90	-0.50951004	-0.44535828	-0.6066513	-0.9482403	-0.95337677	-0.87716293	-0.5418339	-0.56494904
418.1077	4.34	9	-19.406227	-19.407225	-19.39549	-19.347189	-19.416286	-19.453854	-19.512691	-19.378508
676.3668	6.5881658	54	-0.42839432	-0.48464966	-0.5292301	-1.0325966	-1.1065388	-1.1290264	-0.23746109	-0.13358879
442.2562	5.6405997	90	0.09929466	0.027256012	-0.006464004	-0.30669594	-0.24886131	-0.32316017	-1.1404934	-1.411478
372.1416	5.1336665	54	-0.97328186	-1.0009747	-0.93605804	-0.8484497	-0.93244743	-0.9192581	-0.41562462	-0.31750298
378.1499	8.186835	54	-0.6697426	-0.7282696	-0.75938606	-1.3092232	-1.4129448	-1.5049744	-0.42810822	-0.38665962
402.1886	4.204858	63	-0.035900116	-0.7844219	-0.103271484	-0.33198547	-0.6845436	-0.7602787	-0.5313206	-0.09610176
374.1937	4.9244456	81	-0.29225922	-0.33822632	-0.2978649	-0.64554024	-0.63949966	-0.64237976	-0.3272171	-0.2710247
314.079	5.612677	81	-2.780447	-2.992508	-2.917574	-0.9053478	-0.8931923	-0.8496151	-1.498682	-1.3899727
120.0436	6.157963	80	-0.5917454	-0.67572975	-0.6093464	-0.6057129	-0.3427601	-0.3211918	-0.859108	-0.7100315
460.2686	5.1853743	72	0.11119652	0.0981369	0.10170555	-0.32795334	-0.36467934	-0.37455368	-0.9248924	-0.81495094
690.3592	7.0343995	45	-1.0576038	-1.2894287	-1.2547855	-1.8788033	-2.2194633	-2.114151	-1.1549244	-1.3357162
361.0876	5.071501	18	-19.406227	-19.407225	-19.39549	-19.347189	-19.416286	-19.453854	-19.512691	-19.378508
214.1572	5.869166	54	-19.406227	-19.407225	-19.39549	-19.347189	-19.416286	-19.453854	-19.512691	-19.378508
816.8992	5.0869994	81	-19.406227	-19.407225	-19.39549	-19.347189	-19.416286	-19.453854	-19.512691	-19.378508
720.1685	5.0224004	45	-4.136918	-3.6952887	-3.9999905	-1.6916237	-1.2168102	-1.0133858	-2.9880123	-2.968752

Mass	Retention Time	Frequency	normalized_6PP_R1_1: Log2	normalized_6PP_R1_2: Log2	normalized_6PP_R1_3: Log2	normalized_6PP_R2_1: Log2	normalized_6PP_R2_2: Log2	normalized_6PP_R2_3: Log2	normalized_6PP_R3_1: Log2	normalized_6PP_R3_2: Log2
468.22	5.1904993	72	-1.2978611	-1.2614918	-1.3253384	-0.9122143	-0.95355225	-0.9451771	-1.3038845	-1.2647152
369.178	4.938712	63	-0.9124546	-0.95703125	-0.9488163	-1.3053322	-1.3382301	-1.3596878	-1.8400383	-1.790657
708.2265	5.029123	72	-2.019287	-1.5521984	-1.7547932	-1.8105698	-1.570797	-1.5515556	-3.5169249	-3.1323051
708.2263	5.082499	36	-2.16687	-2.1688747	-2.459694	-1.2423859	-1.4506893	-1.5324898	-3.438383	-3.1799278
422.1706	4.4557137	63	-2.2727642	-2.1608448	-2.454855	-3.2365017	-3.0490093	-2.6939392	-2.6513386	-3.0788689
716.2694	5.6625004	18	-19.406227	-19.407225	-19.39549	-19.347189	-19.416286	-19.453854	-19.512691	-19.378508
194.0574	4.158668	27	-19.406227	-19.407225	-19.39549	-19.347189	-19.416286	-19.453854	-19.512691	-19.378508
162.1529	5.037225	81	-2.1343174	-2.4471111	-2.225174	-0.14767265	-0.20700455	-0.23570442	-0.4352913	-0.30554008
448.1215	2.2654998	18	-19.406227	-19.407225	-19.39549	-19.347189	-19.416286	-19.453854	-19.512691	-19.378508
778.4268	7.103	9	-19.406227	-19.407225	-19.39549	-19.347189	-19.416286	-19.453854	-19.512691	-19.378508
136.0521	4.103334	27	-19.406227	-19.407225	-19.39549	-19.347189	-19.416286	-19.453854	-19.512691	-19.378508
488.3499	6.570999	27	-19.406227	-19.407225	-19.39549	-19.347189	-19.416286	-19.453854	-19.512691	-19.378508
967.008	6.552001	36	-19.406227	-19.407225	-19.39549	-19.347189	-19.416286	-19.453854	-19.512691	-19.378508
407.1728	4.2443337	27	-19.406227	-19.407225	-19.39549	-19.347189	-19.416286	-19.453854	-19.512691	-19.378508
434.2136	4.4777765	81	-0.31173897	-0.37145233	-0.6504135	-0.81523323	-0.6595974	-0.43467903	-0.34661865	-0.6162071
434.2153	4.2749987	72	0.34917068	0.21382141	0.032596588	-0.54071045	-0.4875698	-0.2944107	-0.008638382	-0.26408386
700.388	6.8706656	54	-1.1525917	-1.1362133	-1.1169224	-1.8629627	-2.1619415	-2.092081	-1.0445061	-1.1139145
353.1834	5.243001	18	-19.406227	-19.407225	-19.39549	-19.347189	-19.416286	-19.453854	-19.512691	-19.378508
836.3684	4.9227133	63	-19.406227	-19.407225	-19.39549	-19.347189	-19.416286	-19.453854	-19.512691	-19.378508
714.3433	6.476252	36	-0.52552414	-0.6038151	-0.65047264	-0.9234333	-1.1977482	-1.2015438	-0.4498806	-0.6285801
578.5987	5.0404015	45	-19.406227	-19.407225	-19.39549	-19.347189	-19.416286	-19.453854	-19.512691	-19.378508
323.2094	6.07	9	-19.406227	-19.407225	-19.39549	-19.347189	-19.416286	-19.453854	-19.512691	-19.378508
668.6835	5.0499997	9	-19.406227	-19.407225	-19.39549	-19.347189	-19.416286	-19.453854	-19.512691	-19.378508
432.1992	4.355856	63	-1.4182911	-1.2320805	-1.5638695	-1.7651138	-1.7847118	-1.3254662	-1.1631775	-1.404356
376.2113	5.256	9	-19.406227	-19.407225	-19.39549	-19.347189	-19.416286	-19.453854	-19.512691	-19.378508
720.7246	4.958	9	-19.406227	-19.407225	-19.39549	-19.347189	-19.416286	-19.453854	-19.512691	-19.378508
721.7168	4.958	9	-19.406227	-19.407225	-19.39549	-19.347189	-19.416286	-19.453854	-19.512691	-19.378508
556.1216	4.6059995	9	-19.406227	-19.407225	-19.39549	-19.347189	-19.416286	-19.453854	-19.512691	-19.378508
360.0843	5.0149975	36	-1.1486473	-0.70532227	-0.8829231	-0.24521446	0.06574631	0.09086418	-1.5265541	-1.0065746
326.0632	4.152001	18	-19.406227	-19.407225	-19.39549	-19.347189	-19.416286	-19.453854	-19.512691	-19.378508
162.0316	5.006001	18	-2.2683067	-2.2198925	-2.3646946	-0.56677437	-0.6919403	-0.75187683	-1.3672867	-1.235632
314.0788	5.49	9	-19.406227	-19.407225	-19.39549	-19.347189	-19.416286	-19.453854	-19.512691	-19.378508
180.0427	2.3619998	9	-19.406227	-19.407225	-19.39549	-19.347189	-19.416286	-19.453854	-19.512691	-19.378508
162.0315	5.494	9	-19.406227	-19.407225	-19.39549	-19.347189	-19.416286	-19.453854	-19.512691	-19.378508
448.1947	3.9556675	27	-19.406227	-19.407225	-19.39549	-19.347189	-19.416286	-19.453854	-19.512691	-19.378508
628.1581	5.6339993	9	-19.406227	-19.407225	-19.39549	-19.347189	-19.416286	-19.453854	-19.512691	-19.378508
294.0379	4.7805014	36	-19.406227	-19.407225	-19.39549	-19.347189	-19.416286	-19.453854	-19.512691	-19.378508
180.0416	4.074	9	-19.406227	-19.407225	-19.39549	-19.347189	-19.416286	-19.453854	-19.512691	-19.378508
138.0319	2.8530002	9	-19.406227	-19.407225	-19.39549	-19.347189	-19.416286	-19.453854	-19.512691	-19.378508
442.2564	5.6120014	18	-19.406227	-19.407225	-19.39549	-19.347189	-19.416286	-19.453854	-19.512691	-19.378508
456.1418	5.899	9	-19.406227	-19.407225	-19.39549	-19.347189	-19.416286	-19.453854	-19.512691	-19.378508
192.0279	0.97614306	21	-0.5749569	-0.46080208	-0.3916149	-19.347189	-19.416286	-19.453854	-0.5635605	-0.2181015
776.3473	4.4456687	27	-19.406227	-19.407225	-19.39549	-19.347189	-19.416286	-19.453854	-19.512691	-19.378508
372.1776	5.2120004	27	-1.5103207	-1.5436974	-1.4972134	-2.003214	-2.0805912	-2.1114407	-1.0466976	-0.90551186
712.2224	4.7630014	36	-19.406227	-19.407225	-19.39549	-19.347189	-19.416286	-19.453854	-19.512691	-19.378508
438.1646	3.9949994	9	0.23868561	0.038419724	0.16150475	-0.24105835	-0.21234894	-0.10315323	0.2542286	0.0
328.2244	5.601333	27	-0.7250023	-0.71700096	-0.7369709	-2.0772781	-2.2079468	-2.167097	-0.8655987	-0.8192673

Mass	Retention Time	Frequency	normalized_6 PP_R1_1: Lo g2	normalized_6 PP_R1_2: Lo g2	normalized_6 PP_R1_3: Lo g2	normalized_6 PP_R2_1: Lo g2	normalized_6 PP_R2_2: Lo g2	normalized_6 PP_R2_3: Lo g2	normalized_6 PP_R3_1: Lo g2	normalized_6 PP_R3_2: Lo g2
442.2568	5.956	27	-1.1703815	-1.4739323	-1.2410831	-1.0430374	-1.1801834	-1.220398	-1.7433376	-1.6523705
365.1838	7.117	9	-1.278595	-1.449646	-1.3699398	-1.2209282	-1.3046417	-1.6297779	-1.3869495	-1.5088959
804.3791	5.6289988	18	-19.406227	-19.407225	-19.39549	-19.347189	-19.416286	-19.453854	-19.512691	-19.378508
634.2107	4.622	9	-19.406227	-19.407225	-19.39549	-19.347189	-19.416286	-19.453854	-19.512691	-19.378508
434.2138	4.6440005	9	-19.406227	-19.407225	-19.39549	-19.347189	-19.416286	-19.453854	-19.512691	-19.378508

normalized_6PP_R3_3: Log2	normalized_76A_R1_1: Log2	normalized_76A_R1_2: Log2	normalized_76A_R1_3: Log2	normalized_76A_R2_1: Log2	normalized_76A_R2_2: Log2	normalized_76A_R2_3: Log2	normalized_76A_R3_1: Log2	normalized_76A_R3_2: Log2	normalized_76A_R3_3: Log2	normalized_BIO+6PP_R1_1: Log2
2.9068737	0.3956356	0.37434196	0.4163723	3.2379093	3.2302055	3.253378	1.2260971	1.2672195	1.3330326	1.8532887
3.6445293	1.5833855	1.598732	1.6255322	2.683176	2.7008152	2.7124805	1.964037	1.9847488	2.1030731	1.9842949
-19.320137	-1.4628792	-1.4643326	-1.5081196	1.8863277	1.905016	1.8759384	-1.9887104	-1.8880043	-1.8347893	0.44599533
2.635727	0.31754303	0.22481346	0.1958332	-2.1795464	-2.1492023	-2.2770596	-0.18022919	-0.3068695	-0.21840286	2.0856743
2.1556873	0.81941223	0.75102234	0.7239971	2.8851566	2.9144459	2.87319	0.4332409	0.5203934	0.60279274	1.238514
2.1686363	1.2112408	1.3566151	1.5121174	1.5534134	1.6727371	1.2916546	1.4502335	1.5726318	1.9135113	1.1092682
1.8901291	-19.654661	-19.641304	-19.626213	-19.908775	-19.943123	-19.883076	-19.726097	-19.662367	-19.60322	1.2469101
-1.4129658	-1.5323296	-1.3559475	-0.8295803	1.059761	-1.2888947	0.55631256	1.2621555	-1.2433739	-0.762619	-1.4645901
1.4636631	0.0	-0.19000244	-0.11173248	0.81158066	0.64476967	0.8873882	0.52810097	0.53391266	0.42781067	-20.027205
-0.11885071	-0.1328144	-0.17978668	-0.1709652	0.111356735	0.053812027	-0.17357826	0.12648964	0.15291786	0.47714806	-0.69376945
-0.06375313	0.36888504	0.41705132	0.4218979	-0.65507126	-0.56902504	-0.7293892	0.0968647	0.20405579	0.3154316	-0.22395515
1.0427341	-0.47271538	-0.65452194	-0.56318474	0.37173462	0.22470665	0.4664364	0.12308884	0.119298935	0.0	-20.027205
-19.320137	-19.654661	-19.641304	-19.626213	-19.908775	-19.943123	-19.883076	-19.726097	-19.662367	-19.60322	-20.027205
-19.320137	-19.654661	-19.641304	-19.626213	-19.908775	-19.943123	-19.883076	-19.726097	-19.662367	-19.60322	-20.027205
-19.320137	-19.654661	-19.641304	-19.626213	-19.908775	-19.943123	-19.883076	-19.726097	-19.662367	-19.60322	-20.027205
-19.320137	-1.4246464	-1.531683	-1.4746914	-0.22099876	-0.23653793	-0.13546562	-1.0696335	-1.014267	-1.0124474	-20.027205
0.35443687	0.60004044	0.6411457	0.6450043	-0.13609314	-0.19952774	-0.14120102	0.4103489	0.48056793	0.5057297	0.38505936
0.371006	0.7060375	0.7131767	0.89494896	-0.47783852	-0.53097725	-0.52204895	0.55758476	0.7464409	0.7497673	0.22785568
-19.320137	-19.654661	-19.641304	-19.626213	-19.908775	-19.943123	-19.883076	-19.726097	-19.662367	-19.60322	-20.027205
-19.320137	-19.654661	-19.641304	-19.626213	-19.908775	-19.943123	-19.883076	-19.726097	-19.662367	-19.60322	-1.2062092
0.555542	0.36174393	0.6472454	0.5928211	0.18874931	0.29529	0.23782921	0.60087776	0.68981934	0.86623764	0.25491714
-19.320137	-19.654661	-19.641304	-19.626213	-19.908775	-19.943123	-19.883076	-19.726097	-19.662367	-19.60322	-20.027205
-19.320137	-19.654661	-19.641304	-19.626213	-19.908775	-19.943123	-19.883076	-19.726097	-19.662367	-19.60322	-20.027205
-0.56716347	-19.654661	-19.641304	-19.626213	-19.908775	-19.943123	-19.883076	-19.726097	-19.662367	-19.60322	-20.027205
-0.41215324	-0.39796257	-0.46590805	-0.4419632	-0.47444725	-0.7270775	-0.5443516	-0.3344822	-0.4549904	-0.6794834	-0.5569229
-0.012247086	0.29517174	0.4837265	0.43512726	-0.3787899	-0.059310913	-0.33752632	0.17798424	0.371809	0.6172943	0.22033691
0.76019096	-0.22616768	-0.061800003	-0.34367943	0.9222965	0.8365879	1.0383606	-0.42225838	-0.6245384	-0.27420044	0.15489197
-19.320137	-19.654661	-19.641304	-19.626213	-19.908775	-19.943123	-19.883076	-19.726097	-19.662367	-19.60322	-20.027205
-2.251999	-19.654661	-19.641304	-19.626213	-19.908775	-19.943123	-19.883076	-19.726097	-19.662367	-19.60322	-20.027205
-19.320137	-19.654661	-19.641304	-19.626213	-19.908775	-19.943123	-19.883076	-19.726097	-19.662367	-19.60322	-2.330576
-2.0643978	-19.654661	-19.641304	-19.626213	-19.908775	-19.943123	-19.883076	-19.726097	-19.662367	-19.60322	-2.3097687
-0.4954548	-3.608986	-2.57135	-3.5736237	-4.1703405	-3.9920883	-4.194607	-3.6305141	-3.5130577	-3.4017467	-1.3423443
-19.320137	-19.654661	-19.641304	-19.626213	-19.908775	-19.943123	-19.883076	-19.726097	-19.662367	-19.60322	-20.027205
-0.04575348	-0.4225235	-0.39879036	-0.43725014	-0.5410156	-0.5991802	-0.5624428	-0.16168976	-0.09708214	-0.10915947	-20.027205
-0.9681244	-0.44371223	-0.32617378	-0.35193443	-1.8386803	-1.862196	-2.2354698	-0.61523056	-0.7136173	-0.546051	-0.90119743
-0.3382492	-0.4907112	-0.45850945	-0.44519806	-1.8025608	-1.7174454	-1.6984577	-0.9020157	-0.91960335	-0.7279377	-20.027205
-0.4098568	-0.9039383	-0.9151821	-0.92113304	-0.86411095	-0.9761448	-0.91976166	-0.5124798	-0.48960114	-0.45526123	-0.9994011
-0.20241165	-0.4571476	-0.17285156	-0.4586811	-0.49803925	-0.8780613	-0.77126884	-0.052396774	0.05491829	-0.23759842	-0.3623886
-0.21424103	-0.2969799	-0.24473381	-0.29491806	-0.9755211	-0.92733	-0.97485924	-0.30241585	-0.23666573	-0.12698364	-0.87230873
-1.399826	0.6396103	0.6503315	0.69374657	1.9410591	1.8968277	1.9387817	0.55127907	0.6494255	0.64900017	-2.2523346
-0.3655262	-0.8738289	-0.8838749	-0.8175163	-1.1740456	-1.2682514	-1.2360802	-0.82582855	-0.7289753	-0.7023258	-0.67957115
-0.80150414	-0.18209839	-0.2165184	-0.17972755	-1.6658573	-1.6219177	-1.5669975	-0.54130363	-0.5755005	-0.40509987	-0.699728
-1.2511215	-1.0360432	-1.0645981	-1.0925102	-1.0705166	-1.3555393	-1.1526909	-0.83148384	-0.9168186	-1.1515903	-20.027205
-19.320137	-19.654661	-19.641304	-19.626213	-19.908775	-19.943123	-19.883076	-19.726097	-19.662367	-19.60322	-20.027205
-19.320137	-19.654661	-19.641304	-19.626213	-19.908775	-19.943123	-19.883076	-19.726097	-19.662367	-19.60322	-1.476263
-19.320137	-3.0958214	-3.7608595	-3.540388	-1.263771	-1.1069832	-1.0595379	-3.1856804	-3.504053	-3.3851109	-1.7909851
-2.387022	-19.654661	-19.641304	-19.626213	-19.908775	-19.943123	-19.883076	-19.726097	-19.662367	-19.60322	-1.6880322

normalized_6PP_R3_3: Log2	normalized_76A_R1_1: Log2	normalized_76A_R1_2: Log2	normalized_76A_R1_3: Log2	normalized_76A_R2_1: Log2	normalized_76A_R2_2: Log2	normalized_76A_R2_3: Log2	normalized_76A_R3_1: Log2	normalized_76A_R3_2: Log2	normalized_76A_R3_3: Log2	normalized_BIO+6PP_R1_1: Log2
-1.2628918	-1.2888851	-1.2786922	-1.2522984	-1.7209644	-1.571392	-1.6098347	-1.3236389	-1.2992325	-1.1191845	-20.027205
-1.732954	-1.1984482	-1.2187557	-1.2077923	-2.0899067	-2.0444088	-2.0586567	-1.3063679	-1.2352409	-1.1058979	-20.027205
-2.9346104	-2.5561466	-2.522049	-2.2904396	-3.1226463	-3.3152618	-2.9298687	-2.66819	-3.2007923	-2.521019	-3.2977428
-3.001171	-2.3121262	-2.2566643	-2.0332088	-2.9674416	-3.1799107	-2.828291	-2.6175213	-2.3031158	-2.5036983	-20.027205
-2.9888687	0.55226517	0.55236244	0.6852169	0.5972004	0.83888435	0.523571	0.69633293	0.9362984	1.0756054	0.6445923
-19.320137	-19.654661	-19.641304	-19.626213	-19.908775	-19.943123	-19.883076	-19.726097	-19.662367	-19.60322	2.0318127
-19.320137	-19.654661	-19.641304	-19.626213	-19.908775	-19.943123	-19.883076	-19.726097	-19.662367	-19.60322	-0.1554451
-0.36496925	-1.4128971	-1.5191536	-1.53788	-0.037836075	0.003084182	-0.07713699	-1.7624607	-1.6718597	-1.5644512	-0.5769348
-19.320137	-19.654661	-19.641304	-19.626213	-19.908775	-19.943123	-19.883076	-19.726097	-19.662367	-19.60322	0.6487751
-19.320137	-19.654661	-19.641304	-19.626213	-19.908775	-19.943123	-19.883076	-19.726097	-19.662367	-19.60322	0.006746292
-19.320137	-19.654661	-19.641304	-19.626213	-19.908775	-19.943123	-19.883076	-19.726097	-19.662367	-19.60322	-0.84557724
-19.320137	-19.654661	-19.641304	-19.626213	-19.908775	-19.943123	-19.883076	-19.726097	-19.662367	-19.60322	-0.61709213
-19.320137	-1.4771538	-1.0348759	-0.99235916	-1.8966637	-2.1720905	-2.506527	-1.2953587	-1.0345554	-2.0987034	-0.08172417
-19.320137	-19.654661	-19.641304	-19.626213	-19.908775	-19.943123	-19.883076	-19.726097	-19.662367	-19.60322	-0.6043205
-0.6835499	-1.1427155	-0.67967796	-0.80779076	-0.90000725	-0.9993019	-1.0610123	-1.0196056	-0.57663155	-0.3829689	-0.9158859
0.017957687	-0.26519203	-0.052352905	-0.2618122	-0.44289207	-0.17424774	-0.54055405	-0.2622776	-0.066963196	-0.116428375	-0.21008301
-1.1052914	-1.3287315	-1.3924541	-1.4844646	-1.8003483	-1.8833199	-1.6905956	-1.0239315	-1.0724926	-1.1833096	-0.8954754
-19.320137	-19.654661	-19.641304	-19.626213	-19.908775	-19.943123	-19.883076	-19.726097	-19.662367	-19.60322	-1.0858994
-19.320137	-0.39516258	-0.36740303	-0.36042213	-1.4327965	-1.4129257	-1.4937096	-0.47793007	-0.37975693	-0.32294273	-0.99603844
-0.35015488	-1.0330849	-0.95422554	-0.99005127	-1.3135147	-1.3417549	-1.2676125	-1.0514431	-1.0430889	-0.98630524	-1.2453556
-19.320137	-19.654661	-19.641304	-19.626213	-19.908775	-19.943123	-19.883076	-19.726097	-19.662367	-19.60322	-1.8858795
-19.320137	-19.654661	-19.641304	-19.626213	-19.908775	-19.943123	-19.883076	-19.726097	-19.662367	-19.60322	-1.6930141
-19.320137	-19.654661	-19.641304	-19.626213	-19.908775	-19.943123	-19.883076	-19.726097	-19.662367	-19.60322	-1.3404522
-1.5330257	-1.7484035	-1.4150791	-1.4679089	-1.7532997	-1.5006485	-2.3105469	-1.8419323	-1.5392303	-1.4179916	-1.9899311
-19.320137	-19.654661	-19.641304	-19.626213	-19.908775	-19.943123	-19.883076	-19.726097	-19.662367	-19.60322	-2.0710278
-19.320137	-19.654661	-19.641304	-19.626213	-19.908775	-19.943123	-19.883076	-19.726097	-19.662367	-19.60322	-20.027205
-19.320137	-19.654661	-19.641304	-19.626213	-19.908775	-19.943123	-19.883076	-19.726097	-19.662367	-19.60322	-20.027205
-19.320137	-19.654661	-19.641304	-19.626213	-19.908775	-19.943123	-19.883076	-19.726097	-19.662367	-19.60322	-20.027205
-19.320137	-19.654661	-19.641304	-19.626213	-19.908775	-19.943123	-19.883076	-19.726097	-19.662367	-19.60322	-20.027205
-19.320137	-19.654661	-19.641304	-19.626213	-19.908775	-19.943123	-19.883076	-19.726097	-19.662367	-19.60322	-20.027205
-0.35303688	-19.654661	-19.641304	-19.626213	-19.908775	-19.943123	-19.883076	-19.726097	-19.662367	-19.60322	-20.027205
-19.320137	-19.654661	-19.641304	-19.626213	-19.908775	-19.943123	-19.883076	-19.726097	-19.662367	-19.60322	-20.027205
-1.1954918	-19.654661	-19.641304	-19.626213	-19.908775	-19.943123	-19.883076	-19.726097	-19.662367	-19.60322	-20.027205
-19.320137	-19.654661	-19.641304	-19.626213	-19.908775	-19.943123	-19.883076	-19.726097	-19.662367	-19.60322	-20.027205
-19.320137	-19.654661	-19.641304	-19.626213	-19.908775	-19.943123	-19.883076	-19.726097	-19.662367	-19.60322	-20.027205
-19.320137	-19.654661	-19.641304	-19.626213	-19.908775	-19.943123	-19.883076	-19.726097	-19.662367	-19.60322	-20.027205
-19.320137	-0.030416489	0.2678299	0.001882553	-0.21720695	0.13502121	-0.15540695	-0.17183304	0.1087265	0.49960136	-20.027205
-19.320137	-19.654661	-19.641304	-19.626213	-19.908775	-19.943123	-19.883076	-19.726097	-19.662367	-19.60322	-20.027205
-19.320137	-19.654661	-19.641304	-19.626213	-19.908775	-19.943123	-19.883076	-19.726097	-19.662367	-19.60322	-20.027205
-19.320137	-19.654661	-19.641304	-19.626213	-19.908775	-19.943123	-19.883076	-19.726097	-19.662367	-19.60322	-20.027205
-19.320137	-19.654661	-19.641304	-19.626213	-19.908775	-19.943123	-19.883076	-19.726097	-19.662367	-19.60322	-20.027205
-19.320137	-19.654661	-19.641304	-19.626213	-19.908775	-19.943123	-19.883076	-19.726097	-19.662367	-19.60322	-20.027205
-0.051136017	-19.654661	-19.641304	-19.626213	-19.908775	-19.943123	-19.883076	-19.726097	-19.662367	-19.60322	-20.027205
-19.320137	-19.654661	-19.641304	-19.626213	-19.908775	-19.943123	-19.883076	-19.726097	-19.662367	-19.60322	-20.027205
-0.88871574	-2.0000114	-1.9650307	-1.8891239	-1.7558231	-1.7314148	-1.6688232	-1.6461849	-1.5813465	-1.5887299	-20.027205
-19.320137	-1.5272255	-1.4631748	-1.4324856	-3.6649876	-3.6059551	-3.5880966	-1.5102329	-1.4742317	-1.3689213	-20.027205
0.0	-19.654661	-19.641304	-19.626213	-19.908775	-19.943123	-19.883076	-19.726097	-19.662367	-19.60322	-20.027205
-0.75156593	-1.6562977	-1.6111221	-1.6618271	-1.2688122	-1.228159	-1.193327	-1.2776718	-1.0322781	-0.9452667	-20.027205

normalized_6 PP_R3_3: Lo g2	normalized_7 6A_R1_1: Lo g2	normalized_7 6A_R1_2: Lo g2	normalized_7 6A_R1_3: Lo g2	normalized_7 6A_R2_1: Lo g2	normalized_7 6A_R2_2: Lo g2	normalized_7 6A_R2_3: Lo g2	normalized_7 6A_R3_1: Lo g2	normalized_7 6A_R3_2: Lo g2	normalized_7 6A_R3_3: Lo g2	normalized_ BIO+6PP_R1 _1: Log2
-1.6922474	-19.654661	-19.641304	-19.626213	-19.908775	-19.943123	-19.883076	-19.726097	-19.662367	-19.60322	-20.027205
-1.4184208	-19.654661	-19.641304	-19.626213	-19.908775	-19.943123	-19.883076	-19.726097	-19.662367	-19.60322	-20.027205
-19.320137	3.3430996	3.3282814	3.3736992	1.9334621	1.9286213	1.9428482	2.760538	2.8269196	2.8976917	-20.027205
-19.320137	-1.4039555	-1.4500237	-1.3999977	-2.3521938	-2.3179054	-2.3877048	-1.4824448	-1.4040451	-1.2961044	-20.027205
-19.320137	-19.654661	-19.641304	-19.626213	-19.908775	-19.943123	-19.883076	-19.726097	-19.662367	-19.60322	-20.027205

normalized_BIO+6PP_R1_2: Log2	normalized_BIO+6PP_R1_3: Log2	normalized_BIO+6PP_R2_1: Log2	normalized_BIO+6PP_R2_2: Log2	normalized_BIO+6PP_R2_3: Log2	normalized_BIO+6PP_R3_1: Log2	normalized_BIO+6PP_R3_2: Log2	normalized_BIO+6PP_R3_3: Log2	normalized_BIO+76A_R1_1: Log2	normalized_BIO+76A_R1_2: Log2	normalized_BIO+76A_R1_3: Log2
1.8666153	1.9444542	2.9755821	2.9393845	2.937149	0.7138119	0.6229687	0.6276417	2.1955109	2.266405	2.2111416
1.9731369	2.0832443	2.436533	2.4020767	2.4010887	1.7313366	1.644495	1.6580601	2.302267	2.3909054	2.3377953
0.40102005	0.5107975	2.0168324	2.0526543	2.001749	-2.5562592	-2.409052	-2.401743	0.4086094	0.4637909	0.42001915
2.2031422	2.1594162	1.4740429	1.4371853	1.4210587	1.9561996	1.8377934	1.9632778	2.101183	2.194849	2.1277409
1.1299477	1.2451458	1.8305855	1.9072742	1.8334484	-0.25317383	0.018230438	0.012294769	2.0175915	2.069542	2.012844
1.1462154	1.4090157	1.13381	1.196312	1.1476612	1.7419071	1.6436062	1.7905369	1.5696259	1.5207767	1.558815
1.3308773	1.2171135	1.7279377	1.7805119	1.6804028	1.493622	0.40915108	0.68255424	-19.761726	-19.70292	-19.755829
-1.2341442	-1.1381607	-1.9965382	-2.006775	-2.0385704	-0.3966961	-0.91929436	-0.49441147	-1.1171875	-0.886816	-0.99980354
-20.046024	-19.952452	-20.16228	-20.181906	-20.175547	-19.493622	-19.486994	-19.465107	-19.761726	-19.70292	-19.755829
-0.71468925	-0.39696884	-0.6917019	-0.15031242	-0.70126534	0.64600945	0.21715355	0.4105091	0.12669563	-0.036468506	0.053770065
-0.31933403	-0.15745926	-0.8155155	-0.9028816	-0.91671944	-1.4299946	-1.5683289	-1.5947361	-0.8085079	-0.67360497	-0.81406784
-20.046024	-19.952452	-20.16228	-20.181906	-20.175547	-19.493622	-19.486994	-19.465107	-19.761726	-19.70292	-19.755829
-20.046024	-19.952452	-20.16228	-20.181906	-20.175547	-19.493622	-19.486994	-19.465107	-19.761726	-19.70292	-19.755829
-20.046024	-19.952452	-20.16228	-20.181906	-20.175547	-19.493622	-19.486994	-19.465107	-19.761726	-19.70292	-19.755829
-20.046024	-19.952452	-20.16228	-20.181906	-20.175547	-19.493622	-19.486994	-19.465107	-19.761726	-19.70292	-19.755829
-20.046024	-19.952452	-20.16228	-20.181906	-20.175547	-19.493622	-19.486994	-19.465107	-19.761726	-19.70292	-19.755829
0.38498116	0.47517204	0.3615589	0.33667946	0.35587692	0.71887016	0.6223316	0.6390629	0.6763725	0.71910095	0.71017075
0.46403313	0.3399372	-0.06595993	-0.29954338	-0.19188881	0.6251087	0.5886116	0.6975231	-0.5193119	-0.45220375	-0.4796772
-20.046024	-19.952452	-20.16228	-20.181906	-20.175547	-19.493622	-19.486994	-19.465107	-19.761726	-19.70292	-19.755829
-1.2900486	-1.1741829	-0.61621475	-0.5395355	-0.63555336	-2.6291084	-2.458765	-2.4003754	-1.0214176	-0.9443817	-1.0226784
0.046310425	0.3862648	0.12517929	0.12018204	0.0	0.68390846	0.754446	0.7482414	0.40769768	0.46269608	0.41225243
-20.046024	-19.952452	-20.16228	-20.181906	-20.175547	-19.493622	-19.486994	-19.465107	-19.761726	-19.70292	-19.755829
-20.046024	-19.952452	-20.16228	-20.181906	-20.175547	-19.493622	-19.486994	-19.465107	-19.761726	-19.70292	-19.755829
-20.046024	-19.952452	-20.16228	-20.181906	-20.175547	-19.493622	-19.486994	-19.465107	-19.761726	-19.70292	-19.755829
-0.65810585	-0.5505371	-1.0522308	-1.1160679	-1.1300926	-0.5110264	-0.6438694	-0.6316242	-1.1454506	-1.1846714	-1.179884
0.2230568	0.29930115	-0.01996231	-0.04745674	0.04607773	0.5043316	0.58764076	0.60952187	0.37337685	0.45403862	0.36556244
0.28066635	0.40932083	1.1818714	1.0646057	1.1374741	-0.38113022	-0.42563057	-0.5000458	-1.5029526	-1.5702114	-1.6045456
-20.046024	-19.952452	-20.16228	-20.181906	-20.175547	-19.493622	-19.486994	-19.465107	-19.761726	-19.70292	-19.755829
-20.046024	-19.952452	-20.16228	-20.181906	-20.175547	-19.493622	-19.486994	-19.465107	-19.761726	-19.70292	-19.755829
-2.090908	-1.9072952	-0.93382835	-1.1177521	-0.9711971	-3.5511303	-3.7374392	-3.7892046	-2.1929913	-2.0246716	-2.1689663
-2.514164	-2.5038204	-0.7895775	-0.6825695	-0.7957401	-5.9700603	-5.4285784	-5.3831253	-2.2271347	-2.150402	-2.1722107
-0.92829895	-1.0666523	-1.2003803	-1.1816921	-1.1823597	-0.60357094	-0.68450546	-0.7446499	-0.44088554	-0.38134766	-0.43995857
-20.046024	-19.952452	-20.16228	-20.181906	-20.175547	-19.493622	-19.486994	-19.465107	-19.761726	-19.70292	-19.755829
-20.046024	-19.952452	-20.16228	-20.181906	-20.175547	-19.493622	-19.486994	-19.465107	-19.761726	-19.70292	-19.755829
-0.7409191	-0.88615036	-1.5682831	-1.5522823	-1.4743042	-0.73441696	-0.84448814	-0.73729324	-0.49183273	-0.4697113	-0.54930305
-20.046024	-19.952452	-20.16228	-20.181906	-20.175547	-19.493622	-19.486994	-19.465107	-19.761726	-19.70292	-19.755829
-1.0443764	-0.9596443	-1.8268414	-1.8720665	-1.912283	-1.6704788	-1.9900684	-2.0220108	-19.761726	-19.70292	-19.755829
-0.5792179	-0.23027992	-0.46802902	-0.48288918	-0.860054	-0.16117096	0.039274216	0.035827637	-0.29942894	-0.23998642	-0.2907486
-1.0744095	-0.87734795	-1.2935295	-1.2988243	-1.3050537	-0.3870659	-0.3238716	-0.28353882	-0.6699314	-0.57969856	-0.6232853
-2.2780209	-2.249569	-1.6170025	-1.596344	-1.6596584	0.65987206	-3.1908302	-3.226534	1.1674194	1.2346382	1.1619244
-0.8136635	-0.7116566	-1.1142292	-0.6624603	-0.79478645	-0.74978065	-0.4248371	-0.88702965	-1.3929863	-1.3114052	-0.9483013
-0.7048359	-0.5825691	-1.2645702	-1.2610588	-1.2563782	-0.26189804	-0.22681427	-0.19169617	-0.10621643	-0.042676926	-0.11750221
-20.046024	-19.952452	-20.16228	-20.181906	-20.175547	-19.493622	-19.486994	-19.465107	-2.0214252	-2.110632	-2.100319
-20.046024	-19.952452	-20.16228	-20.181906	-20.175547	-19.493622	-19.486994	-19.465107	-19.761726	-19.70292	-19.755829
-1.4765987	-1.3866768	-1.5125294	-1.5505505	-1.5841331	-2.50033	-2.5440216	-2.471262	-2.2423592	-2.1644135	-2.23485
-2.0938625	-2.099533	-1.3778648	-1.297554	-1.3765049	-3.493225	-3.0931187	-3.0449982	-1.5420055	-1.501482	-1.6227264
-1.6547432	-1.6221695	-0.5731735	-0.8726692	-0.5920601	-2.8631554	-3.0768242	-3.089203	-19.761726	-19.70292	-19.755829

normalized_BIO+6PP_R1_2: Log2	normalized_BIO+6PP_R1_3: Log2	normalized_BIO+6PP_R2_1: Log2	normalized_BIO+6PP_R2_2: Log2	normalized_BIO+6PP_R2_3: Log2	normalized_BIO+6PP_R3_1: Log2	normalized_BIO+6PP_R3_2: Log2	normalized_BIO+6PP_R3_3: Log2	normalized_BIO+76A_R1_1: Log2	normalized_BIO+76A_R1_2: Log2	normalized_BIO+76A_R1_3: Log2
-20.046024	-19.952452	-20.16228	-20.181906	-20.175547	-19.493622	-19.486994	-19.465107	-1.657732	-1.6254425	-1.6424522
-20.046024	-19.952452	-20.16228	-20.181906	-20.175547	-19.493622	-19.486994	-19.465107	-1.637434	-1.5714703	-1.6054077
-3.1542892	-3.229992	-2.802599	-3.330902	-2.7797527	-3.0108776	-3.5001526	-3.3223019	-19.761726	-19.70292	-19.755829
-20.046024	-19.952452	-20.16228	-20.181906	-20.175547	-19.493622	-19.486994	-19.465107	-19.761726	-19.70292	-19.755829
0.63487244	0.7387409	0.45702553	0.44523048	0.45027733	1.1773796	1.0999508	1.1270237	0.70866966	0.82378006	0.71845436
2.0382824	2.1193752	1.91605	1.9112797	1.8855343	0.87545776	0.86397934	0.8770447	-19.761726	-19.70292	-19.755829
-0.1424408	-0.051303864	0.25273132	0.22972107	0.1947174	-0.22436142	-0.4032421	-0.3869171	0.56723595	0.65911865	0.58740807
-0.690218	-0.5843048	-0.008342743	0.07876587	0.016166687	-1.9872761	-1.7773037	-1.8030567	-0.43669128	-0.37487793	-0.44390488
0.67329216	0.77396774	0.79577065	0.7831516	0.80470276	1.1503944	1.167366	1.1733074	1.4705544	1.4996376	1.4481564
-0.069337845	-0.007614135	0.2999363	0.18522453	0.19321442	0.55988884	0.46081924	0.45097733	-19.761726	-19.70292	-19.755829
-0.9154434	-0.7266846	0.024539948	0.03350258	0.021688461	-0.5552616	-0.45651817	-0.4874153	-0.08960152	-0.01241684	-0.07967758
-0.6464958	-0.59837914	0.0	-0.010633469	0.012300491	0.5399208	0.3994465	0.41480637	-19.761726	-19.70292	-19.755829
-0.27446175	-0.19117165	-0.8166313	-0.66993713	-0.71876144	-0.2708416	-0.3519268	-0.50110245	-1.5066643	-1.1832161	-1.0259285
-0.41104126	-0.45487976	-1.1011124	-1.0543842	-1.0065899	-1.5868855	-1.6753178	-1.753912	-1.0087261	-1.1230221	-1.1274986
-0.7535248	-0.62795067	-1.0836849	-1.3489685	-0.91018105	-0.84086037	-0.60993195	-0.61767197	-0.666811	-0.64653397	-0.66562843
-0.25790977	-0.20639801	-0.63949203	-0.4124298	-0.38627625	0.35152817	0.081113815	-0.08159065	-0.051805496	0.0	-0.06418228
-0.877058	-0.7817097	-1.7244301	-1.7572556	-1.7698231	-1.6355801	-1.7191906	-1.7447815	-1.9474754	-1.9791737	-1.9528332
-1.079401	-1.0160236	-1.8740673	-1.9101467	-1.9169121	-2.0136204	-2.1066933	-2.0509586	-19.761726	-19.70292	-19.755829
-1.0000267	-0.8957634	-1.5679436	-1.620409	-1.6267014	-0.54937935	-0.62295914	-0.6160183	-1.0371284	-0.95131874	-1.0094986
-1.0136738	-0.94373894	-1.2951298	-1.2464943	-1.3244438	-0.92770576	-0.92272186	-0.9230232	-19.761726	-19.70292	-19.755829
-1.971632	-1.855011	-1.2903595	-1.186655	-1.3185806	-3.0421371	-2.8832073	-2.8836422	-1.6893158	-1.6147137	-1.680893
-1.7492104	-1.6183834	-1.5225849	-1.5090694	-1.5188084	-3.4298477	-3.4057198	-3.4381504	-19.761726	-19.70292	-19.755829
-1.5024414	-1.435751	-1.4520416	-1.4080772	-1.4504986	-3.7356853	-3.599988	-3.6008244	-19.761726	-19.70292	-19.755829
-1.5883312	-1.4151306	-1.5893936	-1.6634407	-1.63233	-1.5682182	-1.6060467	-1.3346176	-1.5385914	-1.384594	-1.6027565
-2.0177574	-1.9026775	-2.0266857	-2.0175533	-2.0345879	-2.28656	-2.2333584	-2.333702	-19.761726	-19.70292	-19.755829
-20.046024	-19.952452	-20.16228	-20.181906	-20.175547	-19.493622	-19.486994	-19.465107	-19.761726	-19.70292	-19.755829
-20.046024	-19.952452	-20.16228	-20.181906	-20.175547	-19.493622	-19.486994	-19.465107	-19.761726	-19.70292	-19.755829
-20.046024	-19.952452	-20.16228	-20.181906	-20.175547	-19.493622	-19.486994	-19.465107	-19.761726	-19.70292	-19.755829
-20.046024	-19.952452	-20.16228	-20.181906	-20.175547	-19.493622	-19.486994	-19.465107	-19.761726	-19.70292	-19.755829
-20.046024	-19.952452	-20.16228	-20.181906	-20.175547	-19.493622	-19.486994	-19.465107	0.001346588	0.10720444	0.041275024
-20.046024	-19.952452	-20.16228	-20.181906	-20.175547	-19.493622	-19.486994	-19.465107	-19.761726	-19.70292	-19.755829
-20.046024	-19.952452	-20.16228	-20.181906	-20.175547	-19.493622	-19.486994	-19.465107	-19.761726	-19.70292	-19.755829
-20.046024	-19.952452	-20.16228	-20.181906	-20.175547	-19.493622	-19.486994	-19.465107	-19.761726	-19.70292	-19.755829
-20.046024	-19.952452	-20.16228	-20.181906	-20.175547	-19.493622	-19.486994	-19.465107	-19.761726	-19.70292	-19.755829
-20.046024	-19.952452	-20.16228	-20.181906	-20.175547	-19.493622	-19.486994	-19.465107	-19.761726	-19.70292	-19.755829
-20.046024	-19.952452	-20.16228	-20.181906	-20.175547	-19.493622	-19.486994	-19.465107	-1.0253716	-0.973629	-1.0181026
-20.046024	-19.952452	-20.16228	-20.181906	-20.175547	-19.493622	-19.486994	-19.465107	-19.761726	-19.70292	-19.755829
-20.046024	-19.952452	-20.16228	-20.181906	-20.175547	-19.493622	-19.486994	-19.465107	0.7321491	0.83963966	0.76898
-20.046024	-19.952452	-20.16228	-20.181906	-20.175547	-19.493622	-19.486994	-19.465107	0.56578255	0.7064285	0.70103836
-20.046024	-19.952452	-20.16228	-20.181906	-20.175547	-19.493622	-19.486994	-19.465107	0.7411785	0.7946663	0.76210594
-20.046024	-19.952452	-20.16228	-20.181906	-20.175547	-19.493622	-19.486994	-19.465107	-0.4417572	-0.36973953	-0.48568535
-20.046024	-19.952452	-20.16228	-20.181906	-20.175547	-19.493622	-19.486994	-19.465107	-1.5364246	-1.4486122	-1.4804955
-20.046024	-19.952452	-20.16228	-20.181906	-20.175547	-19.493622	-19.486994	-19.465107	-1.6501064	-1.5560188	-1.619688
-20.046024	-19.952452	-20.16228	-20.181906	-20.175547	-19.493622	-19.486994	-19.465107	-1.3918953	-1.3420353	-1.428978
-20.046024	-19.952452	-20.16228	-20.181906	-20.175547	-19.493622	-19.486994	-19.465107	-19.761726	-19.70292	-19.755829
-20.046024	-19.952452	-20.16228	-20.181906	-20.175547	-19.493622	-19.486994	-19.465107	-19.761726	-19.70292	-19.755829

normalized_ BIO+6PP_R1 _2: Log2	normalized_ BIO+6PP_R1 _3: Log2	normalized_ BIO+6PP_R2 _1: Log2	normalized_ BIO+6PP_R2 _2: Log2	normalized_ BIO+6PP_R2 _3: Log2	normalized_ BIO+6PP_R3 _1: Log2	normalized_ BIO+6PP_R3 _2: Log2	normalized_ BIO+6PP_R3 _3: Log2	normalized_ BIO+76A_R1 _1: Log2	normalized_ BIO+76A_R1 _2: Log2	normalized_ BIO+76A_R1 _3: Log2
-20.046024	-19.952452	-20.16228	-20.181906	-20.175547	-19.493622	-19.486994	-19.465107	-19.761726	-19.70292	-19.755829
-20.046024	-19.952452	-20.16228	-20.181906	-20.175547	-19.493622	-19.486994	-19.465107	-19.761726	-19.70292	-19.755829
-20.046024	-19.952452	-20.16228	-20.181906	-20.175547	-19.493622	-19.486994	-19.465107	-19.761726	-19.70292	-19.755829
-20.046024	-19.952452	-20.16228	-20.181906	-20.175547	-19.493622	-19.486994	-19.465107	-19.761726	-19.70292	-19.755829
-20.046024	-19.952452	-20.16228	-20.181906	-20.175547	-19.493622	-19.486994	-19.465107	-19.761726	-19.70292	-19.755829

normalized_ BIO+76A_R2 _1: Log2	normalized_ BIO+76A_R2 _2: Log2	normalized_ BIO+76A_R2 _3: Log2	normalized_ BIO+76A_R3 _1: Log2	normalized_ BIO+76A_R3 _2: Log2	normalized_ BIO+76A_R3 _3: Log2	normalized_ BIO+T22+76 A_R1_1: Log	normalized_ BIO+T22+76 A_R1_2: Log	normalized_ BIO+T22+76 A_R1_3: Log	normalized_ BIO+T22+76 A_R2_1: Log	normalized_ BIO+T22+76 A_R2_2: Log
2.0552502	2.0419846	1.9715595	2.548603	2.5490303	2.5514736	2.413002	2.4136887	2.3950577	1.9750023	1.9915066
2.237091	2.2380733	2.170147	2.5382538	2.5761948	2.525856	2.3489609	2.3495731	2.317213	2.3006554	2.312542
0.5905628	0.5345688	0.5096111	0.025720596	0.045009613	0.14882278	0.58930016	0.53808403	0.5745945	-1.029419	-1.0301075
3.168932	3.1725826	3.089697	2.1054974	2.0945683	2.0782032	2.078949	2.0403004	2.0648212	2.638054	2.532919
2.1120377	2.024166	2.0248013	1.730463	1.7533112	1.9085026	2.073122	2.0011463	2.0642014	1.0611706	1.0586491
1.3656635	1.3564682	1.4541817	2.0115528	2.0003548	2.0257473	-1.5610085	-1.4024239	-1.5781155	-1.8033047	-1.6475887
-19.894596	-19.90171	-19.976904	-19.702751	-19.701271	-19.709652	1.4029388	1.4093552	1.4698792	0.9657936	0.92323685
-0.9786625	-0.9178848	-0.9902897	-0.8926296	-0.6223507	-0.60354614	0.6677742	0.7702141	0.66487503	0.6953869	0.6935806
-19.894596	-19.90171	-19.976904	-19.702751	-19.701271	-19.709652	0.39073372	0.37534142	0.36021996	0.5517235	0.57878876
-0.046518326	-0.09840584	0.027370453	0.19285011	0.2069664	0.38497543	1.3931541	1.5681686	1.3601074	1.1456757	1.2982311
-0.62854385	-0.6048031	-0.62838554	-0.72311974	-0.73177147	-0.69509697	0.16943741	0.21028137	0.1582241	0.4603157	0.5010967
-19.894596	-19.90171	-19.976904	-19.702751	-19.701271	-19.709652	-0.10638809	-0.13140869	-0.124492645	0.070690155	0.07628822
-19.894596	-19.90171	-19.976904	-19.702751	-19.701271	-19.709652	0.3420105	0.38321495	0.28496742	0.5936928	0.54725266
-19.894596	-19.90171	-19.976904	-19.702751	-19.701271	-19.709652	-19.927736	-19.927612	-19.94545	-19.684807	-19.693811
-19.894596	-19.90171	-19.976904	-19.702751	-19.701271	-19.709652	-19.927736	-19.927612	-19.94545	-19.684807	-19.693811
-19.894596	-19.90171	-19.976904	-19.702751	-19.701271	-19.709652	-0.26763535	-0.23430443	-0.30036926	-0.66825676	-0.6443348
0.27766418	0.26691818	0.17563629	-0.001380920	0.0	-0.031808853	0.40483665	0.41297913	0.16383362	0.48358917	0.25499916
-1.1123791	-1.0836048	-1.1946297	-1.3356171	-1.2932243	-1.3406906	0.18793297	0.08910942	0.15703583	0.5110035	0.56181526
-19.894596	-19.90171	-19.976904	-19.702751	-19.701271	-19.709652	-0.34374237	-0.31295967	-0.4195423	0.0	0.05700493
-0.92783546	-1.0166721	-1.0365906	-1.212986	-1.2016506	-1.0147934	-0.998827	-1.0884914	-1.0035572	-1.729475	-1.7394676
0.42106247	0.40309334	0.35849	0.5073433	0.47684288	0.4928608	0.12588882	0.13414764	0.097099304	0.2676773	0.0
-19.894596	-19.90171	-19.976904	-19.702751	-19.701271	-19.709652	0.2472992	0.32567787	0.24502182	0.31731224	0.37932587
-19.894596	-19.90171	-19.976904	-19.702751	-19.701271	-19.709652	-19.927736	-19.927612	-19.94545	-19.684807	-19.693811
-19.894596	-19.90171	-19.976904	-19.702751	-19.701271	-19.709652	-0.42583656	-0.3966179	-0.4622879	-0.82047844	-0.8077698
-0.49505424	-0.54221725	-0.6244812	-0.42186928	-0.44737625	-0.4715824	-0.4441223	-0.4873562	-0.45746803	-0.12178993	-0.19030952
0.4093876	0.39886475	0.33372116	0.44716072	0.4296379	0.43868446	-0.017902374	-0.015727997	-0.008401871	-0.003101348	0.07821083
-1.5268917	-1.514307	-1.6218891	-1.0899086	-1.1659966	-1.7872238	0.4648075	0.42927742	0.4474926	0.20671654	-0.046037674
-19.894596	-19.90171	-19.976904	-19.702751	-19.701271	-19.709652	-19.927736	-19.927612	-19.94545	-19.684807	-19.693811
-19.894596	-19.90171	-19.976904	-19.702751	-19.701271	-19.709652	0.0	-0.10612869	-0.25699615	0.42449188	0.3780632
-2.3501377	-2.1108913	-2.278572	-2.0551949	-1.9521999	-2.390129	-2.30484	-1.892931	-2.3841991	-2.275854	-2.3420105
-1.745266	-1.9485207	-1.8724899	-2.0487652	-2.1038666	-1.7288265	-1.5695496	-1.972723	-1.5796394	-3.6535797	-3.2353878
-0.4750824	-0.47493172	-0.534565	0.0	-0.016038895	0.0	-0.2486248	-0.3633232	-0.20162201	-0.21449089	-0.19786835
-19.894596	-19.90171	-19.976904	-19.702751	-19.701271	-19.709652	-19.927736	-19.927612	-19.94545	-19.684807	-19.693811
-19.894596	-19.90171	-19.976904	-19.702751	-19.701271	-19.709652	-0.7329254	-0.7673893	-0.7948818	-0.16752815	-0.2864418
-1.0062962	-1.2157822	-1.1169872	-1.5137482	-1.5208187	-1.4147987	-1.1512871	-1.1408482	-1.1404209	-0.65348816	-0.7974949
-19.894596	-19.90171	-19.976904	-19.702751	-19.701271	-19.709652	-19.927736	-19.927612	-19.94545	-19.684807	-19.693811
-19.894596	-19.90171	-19.976904	-19.702751	-19.701271	-19.709652	-1.3026237	-1.3301468	-1.3787594	-1.1546669	-1.1795368
-0.4905815	-0.6838207	-0.35087585	-0.60178566	-0.62918663	-0.2742958	-0.65307426	-0.898098	-0.7985573	-0.6637516	-0.6133537
-0.6485615	-0.6450043	-0.6959114	-0.47719955	-0.42960548	-0.48547363	-0.7754631	-0.7678051	-0.81882095	-0.70105934	-0.61852455
1.3843651	1.3603001	1.2930069	1.4326477	1.4502678	1.4169807	-19.927736	-19.927612	-19.94545	-19.684807	-19.693811
-1.1967144	-1.0902271	-1.2689857	-0.7987366	-0.81529236	-0.86644363	-0.9802036	-0.8310623	-0.63734627	-0.25203896	-0.19816017
-0.8569069	-0.83169556	-0.8560085	-1.1049995	-1.1523075	-1.146944	-0.92593	-0.9570255	-0.9455471	-0.57336235	-0.53125
-0.8023777	-0.8679867	-1.0067558	-1.2352085	-1.2781601	-1.3028698	-19.927736	-19.927612	-19.94545	-19.684807	-19.693811
-19.894596	-19.90171	-19.976904	-19.702751	-19.701271	-19.709652	-19.927736	-19.927612	-19.94545	-19.684807	-19.693811
-1.5972595	-1.6624622	-1.7041912	-1.5727386	-1.5667458	-1.5946484	-19.927736	-19.927612	-19.94545	-19.684807	-19.693811
-1.3506126	-1.6578026	-1.5104008	-1.4853134	-1.4784718	-1.1408157	-1.3924141	-1.6740704	-1.3873692	-2.4696827	-2.3175087
-19.894596	-19.90171	-19.976904	-19.702751	-19.701271	-19.709652	-19.927736	-19.927612	-19.94545	-19.684807	-19.693811

normalized_ BIO+76A_R2 _1: Log2	normalized_ BIO+76A_R2 _2: Log2	normalized_ BIO+76A_R2 _3: Log2	normalized_ BIO+76A_R3 _1: Log2	normalized_ BIO+76A_R3 _2: Log2	normalized_ BIO+76A_R3 _3: Log2	normalized_ BIO+T22+76A _R1_1: Log2	normalized_ BIO+T22+76A _R1_2: Log2	normalized_ BIO+T22+76A _R1_3: Log2	normalized_ BIO+T22+76A _R2_1: Log2	normalized_ BIO+T22+76A _R2_2: Log2
-19.894596	-19.90171	-19.976904	-19.702751	-19.701271	-19.709652	-1.12504	-1.1334724	-1.1414566	-0.54888153	-0.56375694
-19.894596	-19.90171	-19.976904	-19.702751	-19.701271	-19.709652	-19.927736	-19.927612	-19.94545	-19.684807	-19.693811
-19.894596	-19.90171	-19.976904	-19.702751	-19.701271	-19.709652	-19.927736	-19.927612	-19.94545	-19.684807	-19.693811
-19.894596	-19.90171	-19.976904	-19.702751	-19.701271	-19.709652	-19.927736	-19.927612	-19.94545	-19.684807	-19.693811
-19.894596	-19.90171	-19.976904	-19.702751	-19.701271	-19.709652	-0.60842896	-0.36018562	-0.59643364	-0.9556122	-0.7066803

normalized_ BIO+T22+76 A_R2_3: Log	normalized_ BIO+T22+76 A_R3_1: Log	normalized_ BIO+T22+76 A_R3_2: Log	normalized_ BIO+T22+76 A_R3_3: Log	normalized_ BIO+T22_R1 1: Log2	normalized_ BIO+T22_R1 2: Log2	normalized_ BIO+T22_R1 3: Log2	normalized_ BIO+T22_R2 1: Log2	normalized_ BIO+T22_R2 2: Log2	normalized_ BIO+T22_R2 3: Log2	normalized_ BIO+T22_R3 1: Log2
2.0173912	2.98172	3.058363	3.0321255	2.1265392	2.1018238	2.0950527	2.820963	2.8469257	2.8704033	2.4955196
2.3118305	2.540226	2.620905	2.603857	2.2904243	2.2966557	2.2769146	2.579668	2.6383781	2.6645718	2.4540825
-1.0164833	2.061823	2.1153831	2.107109	0.34014702	0.30068016	0.4835701	1.2044277	1.1879387	1.247303	0.35839653
2.7246037	1.755724	1.724741	1.7909985	1.958416	1.9301262	1.8956604	2.988121	3.0305843	3.023634	2.6445618
1.0782719	3.0511684	3.1173706	3.1006374	1.7491417	1.7447891	1.9159298	2.470049	2.4143791	2.5008945	1.901432
-2.0791092	-2.270874	-2.1905823	-2.183506	1.3719158	1.3756618	1.3238564	1.6401653	1.5047207	1.6824818	1.5245991
1.1321907	1.6875267	2.0301418	1.9862671	1.3956757	1.3679848	1.3209591	1.3164291	1.3240871	1.3425274	1.231533
0.4446144	0.56819916	0.64128685	0.5993881	0.37018013	0.45773315	0.3942623	0.8492527	1.0478191	0.8545456	1.008112
0.6809292	0.6472168	0.7211151	0.68686676	0.40219688	0.3870983	0.3421173	0.991148	0.92463684	1.0070915	0.4266262
1.2576694	1.216589	1.2635746	1.1724224	0.0	0.16152573	0.17303658	0.35583305	0.3426342	0.34309006	0.2780056
0.4332714	-0.97509384	-0.9094658	-0.94802475	0.11996651	0.15197372	0.107580185	-0.022649765	0.12856865	0.0	0.4645462
0.22117043	0.17206383	0.20744514	0.16958809	-0.03109932	-0.05466461	-0.07945442	0.56697273	0.52433777	0.5942497	-0.19471931
0.5489006	0.0	-0.0470047	-0.031847	0.26973724	0.34306526	0.24151611	0.2740307	0.4062538	0.31783485	-19.667492
-19.660156	-19.913038	-19.850258	-19.892448	-19.700453	-19.728466	-19.745752	-19.679295	-19.685715	-19.64875	-19.667492
-19.660156	-19.913038	-19.850258	-19.892448	0.018680573	-0.1024971	0.12020683	-0.009286880	-19.685715	-19.64875	-19.667492
-0.5603142	-0.30786133	-0.2094307	-0.5549946	-0.46878433	-0.508152	-0.5276642	-0.4604454	-0.49038315	-0.4273796	-0.72966576
0.51140213	0.4371643	0.522501	0.24487305	0.52394295	0.47924423	0.43632317	0.46201515	0.46545982	0.5145302	0.35150528
0.7054043	-0.06860733	-0.2707615	-0.22856522	0.36758423	0.17342186	0.30942726	0.020690918	0.034500122	0.015871048	0.32712936
-0.01026535	-0.6094742	-0.5774956	-0.5971432	-0.4411564	-0.41000366	-0.40051842	-0.39734077	-0.6390896	-0.34920502	-0.116846085
-1.724432	-0.41453552	-0.33664322	-0.36728287	-1.3307362	-1.3299484	-1.1445789	-0.71006584	-0.7929554	-0.68429947	-1.1949234
0.0	-0.25862312	-0.2645111	-0.20397186	-0.47593117	-0.4230194	-0.7911186	-0.26613426	0.16298676	-0.2039051	-19.667492
-0.15789795	-0.47135925	-0.3672657	-0.42878723	-0.3230343	-0.20195389	-0.22404099	-0.27103806	-0.045280457	-0.1293602	-19.667492
-19.660156	-19.913038	-19.850258	-19.892448	-0.05821991	-0.13843155	0.025493622	-19.679295	-19.685715	-19.64875	-19.667492
-0.92087364	-0.19098854	-0.084724426	-0.06315231	-19.700453	-19.728466	-19.745752	-19.679295	-19.685715	-19.64875	-19.667492
-0.17615128	-0.6012955	-0.6273041	-0.6509037	-19.700453	-19.728466	-19.745752	-19.679295	-19.685715	-19.64875	-19.667492
-0.23211098	-0.55088425	-0.6515312	-0.46050644	-1.0365086	-0.8165722	-0.9438133	-0.78430176	-0.01706314	-0.86796	-19.667492
0.23200417	1.2304058	1.3065014	1.3145142	-19.700453	-19.728466	-19.745752	-19.679295	-19.685715	-19.64875	-19.667492
-19.660156	-19.913038	-19.850258	-19.892448	-19.700453	-19.728466	-19.745752	-19.679295	-19.685715	-19.64875	-19.667492
0.5029335	0.07449722	0.10477066	0.26556587	-19.700453	-19.728466	-19.745752	-19.679295	-19.685715	-19.64875	-19.667492
-2.1540813	-0.952002	-0.91959	-0.9272766	-1.7603569	-1.9914627	-1.9950905	-1.5277328	-1.423809	-1.3690624	-1.7600193
-3.9088993	-1.1921463	-1.1237297	-1.1044312	-3.5551968	-2.8943653	-2.8545265	-1.617712	-1.4732513	-1.6312199	-2.0176525
-0.22344017	-0.42414856	-0.36813545	-0.3775158	-0.6714897	-0.6380329	-0.68252754	-0.27838516	-0.18080139	-0.18955803	-0.22644615
-19.660156	-19.913038	-19.850258	-19.892448	-19.700453	-19.728466	-19.745752	-19.679295	-19.685715	-19.64875	-19.667492
-0.23181915	-1.3984089	-1.3230209	-1.4159718	-19.700453	-19.728466	-19.745752	-19.679295	-19.685715	-19.64875	-19.667492
-0.6129341	-1.2588196	-1.0961018	-1.2575798	-0.5516796	-0.39452362	-0.43126488	-1.7167778	-1.3686638	-1.5014172	-1.0974236
-19.660156	-19.913038	-19.850258	-19.892448	-1.2821388	-1.1945934	-1.1628609	-0.8768654	-0.8064003	-0.7776699	-1.5170155
-1.1824265	-1.5326538	-1.4771214	-1.5582237	-19.700453	-19.728466	-19.745752	-19.679295	-19.685715	-19.64875	-19.667492
-0.894207	-1.1329689	-1.1327686	-1.3287868	-1.3677883	-1.4478912	-1.4284286	-1.2191143	-0.78611565	-1.1632576	-19.667492
-0.44570923	-1.1276188	-1.0450172	-1.0626698	-1.0191116	-0.9465084	-0.9367981	-0.4646759	-0.38591576	-0.40816307	-0.6013832
-19.660156	-19.913038	-19.850258	-19.892448	-1.9093151	-1.9349461	-1.9230328	-1.5673428	-1.5601501	-1.4271488	-2.3692951
-0.076725006	-0.75481606	-0.8397751	-0.9990368	-0.74632263	-0.99960136	-0.97122955	-0.6351528	-0.62638474	-0.58777046	-0.528038
-0.47712135	-1.0709114	-1.0567722	-0.99829674	-0.47517967	-0.41522217	-0.4413376	-1.2338753	-1.2126236	-1.1901474	-0.5846958
-19.660156	-19.913038	-19.850258	-19.892448	-19.700453	-19.728466	-19.745752	-19.679295	-19.685715	-19.64875	-19.667492
-19.660156	-19.913038	-19.850258	-19.892448	-19.700453	-19.728466	-19.745752	-19.679295	-19.685715	-19.64875	-19.667492
-19.660156	-19.913038	-19.850258	-19.892448	-0.9937687	-1.0214958	-1.0372849	-2.444973	-2.4510098	-2.4025574	-1.6161385
-2.531992	-0.9269867	-0.9220009	-0.93844795	-3.1936188	-2.843771	-3.1207848	-1.4687271	-1.6886292	-1.4870033	-1.4772243
-19.660156	-19.913038	-19.850258	-19.892448	-2.2454472	-1.7630081	-2.7440472	-2.8533173	-2.2699146	-3.3749905	-2.8157558

normalized_ BIO+T22+76 A_R2_3: Log	normalized_ BIO+T22+76 A_R3_1: Log	normalized_ BIO+T22+76 A_R3_2: Log	normalized_ BIO+T22+76 A_R3_3: Log	normalized_ BIO+T22_R1 1: Log2	normalized_ BIO+T22_R1 2: Log2	normalized_ BIO+T22_R1 3: Log2	normalized_ BIO+T22_R2 1: Log2	normalized_ BIO+T22_R2 2: Log2	normalized_ BIO+T22_R2 3: Log2	normalized_ BIO+T22_R3 1: Log2
-1.3509331	-1.5255604	-1.5005875	-1.3965931	-1.5067883	-1.3890171	-1.378828	-0.9462681	-0.89001465	-0.87659454	-1.564024
-1.2051182	-2.1181774	-2.0402336	-2.034935	-19.700453	-19.728466	-19.745752	-19.679295	-19.685715	-19.64875	-19.667492
-2.7991657	-3.2465782	-3.5619144	-3.4861946	-19.700453	-19.728466	-19.745752	-19.679295	-19.685715	-19.64875	-19.667492
-19.660156	-19.913038	-19.850258	-19.892448	-19.700453	-19.728466	-19.745752	-19.679295	-19.685715	-19.64875	-19.667492
-19.660156	-19.913038	-19.850258	-19.892448	-1.1269913	-1.0179062	-1.1719093	-0.7671585	-0.6522236	-0.8244686	-0.7738724
-19.660156	-19.913038	-19.850258	-19.892448	-19.700453	-19.728466	-19.745752	-19.679295	-19.685715	-19.64875	-19.667492
-19.660156	-19.913038	-19.850258	-19.892448	-19.700453	-19.728466	-19.745752	-19.679295	-19.685715	-19.64875	-19.667492
-1.1871014	0.14083672	0.21781921	0.18059349	-0.8545799	-0.8645897	-0.6612568	-0.18055725	-0.29488182	-0.19403648	-0.6031666
-19.660156	-19.913038	-19.850258	-19.892448	-19.700453	-19.728466	-19.745752	-19.679295	-19.685715	-19.64875	-19.667492
-19.660156	-19.913038	-19.850258	-19.892448	-19.700453	-19.728466	-19.745752	-19.679295	-19.685715	-19.64875	-19.667492
-19.660156	-19.913038	-19.850258	-19.892448	-19.700453	-19.728466	-19.745752	-19.679295	-19.685715	-19.64875	-19.667492
-1.1812611	-0.28320503	-0.17226982	-0.28396416	-19.700453	-19.728466	-19.745752	-19.679295	-19.685715	-19.64875	-19.667492
-19.660156	-19.913038	-19.850258	-19.892448	-19.700453	-19.728466	-19.745752	-19.679295	-19.685715	-19.64875	-19.667492
-19.660156	-19.913038	-19.850258	-19.892448	-19.700453	-19.728466	-19.745752	-19.679295	-19.685715	-19.64875	-19.667492
-0.38754463	-0.7113342	-0.6026993	-0.66908455	-0.9492359	-0.6653271	-0.9855099	-1.015007	-0.7627163	-0.85287285	-0.39350128
-19.660156	-19.913038	-19.850258	-19.892448	-0.75577736	-0.7054863	-0.80077744	-0.48166466	-0.24798584	-0.45699692	0.101854324
-19.660156	-19.913038	-19.850258	-19.892448	-19.700453	-19.728466	-19.745752	-19.679295	-19.685715	-19.64875	-19.667492
-19.660156	-19.913038	-19.850258	-19.892448	-1.1093426	-1.0800037	-1.0875721	-2.029581	-1.9866905	-1.9476528	-1.4264526
-0.6072674	-1.6247349	-1.5558033	-1.5811615	-1.7955418	-1.7468758	-1.7352409	-0.61424255	-0.5766926	-0.5563202	-0.7521229
-19.660156	-19.913038	-19.850258	-19.892448	-19.700453	-19.728466	-19.745752	-19.679295	-19.685715	-19.64875	-19.667492
-2.2265549	-0.9244976	-0.8726101	-0.88749313	-2.3674812	-2.3287716	-2.2507877	-1.4889603	-1.5758953	-1.4567814	-1.6416702
-19.660156	-19.913038	-19.850258	-19.892448	-19.700453	-19.728466	-19.745752	-19.679295	-19.685715	-19.64875	-19.667492
-19.660156	-19.913038	-19.850258	-19.892448	-19.700453	-19.728466	-19.745752	-19.679295	-19.685715	-19.64875	-19.667492
-19.660156	-19.913038	-19.850258	-19.892448	-19.700453	-19.728466	-19.745752	-19.679295	-19.685715	-19.64875	-19.667492
-19.660156	-19.913038	-19.850258	-19.892448	-19.700453	-19.728466	-19.745752	-19.679295	-19.685715	-19.64875	-19.667492
-19.660156	-19.913038	-19.850258	-19.892448	-19.700453	-19.728466	-19.745752	-19.679295	-19.685715	-19.64875	-19.667492
-19.660156	-19.913038	-19.850258	-19.892448	-19.700453	-19.728466	-19.745752	-19.679295	-19.685715	-19.64875	-19.667492
-19.660156	-19.913038	-19.850258	-19.892448	-19.700453	-19.728466	-19.745752	-19.679295	-19.685715	-19.64875	-19.667492
-19.660156	-19.913038	-19.850258	-19.892448	-19.700453	-19.728466	-19.745752	-19.679295	-19.685715	-19.64875	-19.667492
-19.660156	-19.913038	-19.850258	-19.892448	-19.700453	-19.728466	-19.745752	-19.679295	-19.685715	-19.64875	-19.667492
-19.660156	-19.913038	-19.850258	-19.892448	-19.700453	-19.728466	-19.745752	-19.679295	-19.685715	-19.64875	-19.667492
-19.660156	-19.913038	-19.850258	-19.892448	-19.700453	-19.728466	-19.745752	-19.679295	-19.685715	-19.64875	-19.667492
-19.660156	-19.913038	-19.850258	-19.892448	-19.700453	-19.728466	-19.745752	-19.679295	-19.685715	-19.64875	-19.667492
-19.660156	-19.913038	-19.850258	-19.892448	-19.700453	-19.728466	-19.745752	-19.679295	-19.685715	-19.64875	-19.667492
-19.660156	-19.913038	-19.850258	-19.892448	-19.700453	-19.728466	-19.745752	-19.679295	-19.685715	-19.64875	-19.667492
-19.660156	-19.913038	-19.850258	-19.892448	-19.700453	-19.728466	-19.745752	-19.679295	-19.685715	-19.64875	-19.667492
-19.660156	-19.913038	-19.850258	-19.892448	-19.700453	-19.728466	-19.745752	-19.679295	-19.685715	-19.64875	-19.667492
-19.660156	-19.913038	-19.850258	-19.892448	-19.700453	-19.728466	-19.745752	-19.679295	-19.685715	-19.64875	-19.667492
-19.660156	-19.913038	-19.850258	-19.892448	-19.700453	-19.728466	-19.745752	-19.679295	-19.685715	-19.64875	-19.667492
-19.660156	-19.913038	-19.850258	-19.892448	-19.700453	-19.728466	-19.745752	-19.679295	-19.685715	-19.64875	-19.667492
-19.660156	-19.913038	-19.850258	-19.892448	-1.1634884	-1.162487	-1.1788349	-0.84246826	-0.8375721	-0.7887821	-0.7714424
-19.660156	-19.913038	-19.850258	-19.892448	-19.700453	-19.728466	-19.745752	-19.679295	-19.685715	-19.64875	-19.667492
-19.660156	-19.913038	-19.850258	-19.892448	-19.700453	-19.728466	-19.745752	-19.679295	-19.685715	-19.64875	-19.667492
-19.660156	-19.913038	-19.850258	-19.892448	-19.700453	-19.728466	-19.745752	-19.679295	-19.685715	-19.64875	-19.667492
-19.660156	-19.913038	-19.850258	-19.892448	-19.700453	-19.728466	-19.745752	-19.679295	-19.685715	-19.64875	-19.667492
-19.660156	-19.913038	-19.850258	-19.892448	-19.700453	-19.728466	-19.745752	-19.679295	-19.685715	-19.64875	-19.667492
-19.660156	-19.913038	-19.850258	-19.892448	-19.700453	-19.728466	-19.745752	-19.679295	-19.685715	-19.64875	-19.667492
-19.660156	-19.913038	-19.850258	-19.892448	-19.700453	-19.728466	-19.745752	-19.679295	-19.685715	-19.64875	-19.667492
-19.660156	-19.913038	-19.850258	-19.892448	-19.700453	-19.728466	-19.745752	-19.679295	-19.685715	-19.64875	-19.667492
-19.660156	-19.913038	-19.850258	-19.892448	-19.700453	-19.728466	-19.745752	-19.679295	-19.685715	-19.64875	-19.667492
-19.660156	-19.913038	-19.850258	-19.892448	-1.645546	-1.6283321	-1.657135	-0.9021416	-0.70547676	-0.8118248	-1.1452103
-19.660156	-19.913038	-19.850258	-19.892448	-19.700453	-19.728466	-19.745752	-19.679295	-19.685715	-19.64875	-19.667492
-19.660156	-19.913038	-19.850258	-19.892448	-1.2310963	-1.2145386	-1.3094273	-3.3262863	-3.227068	-3.2717094	-1.7468891
-19.660156	-19.913038	-19.850258	-19.892448	-19.700453	-19.728466	-19.745752	-19.679295	-19.685715	-19.64875	-19.667492
-19.660156	-19.913038	-19.850258	-19.892448	-19.700453	-19.728466	-19.745752	-19.679295	-19.685715	-19.64875	-19.667492

normalized_ BIO+T22+76A _R2_3: Log2	normalized_ BIO+T22+76A _R3_1: Log2	normalized_ BIO+T22+76A _R3_2: Log2	normalized_ BIO+T22+76A _R3_3: Log2	normalized_ BIO+T22_R1_ 1: Log2	normalized_ BIO+T22_R1_ 2: Log2	normalized_ BIO+T22_R1_ 3: Log2	normalized_ BIO+T22_R2_ 1: Log2	normalized_ BIO+T22_R2_ 2: Log2	normalized_ BIO+T22_R2_ 3: Log2	normalized_ BIO+T22_R3_ 1: Log2
-0.5734997	-1.081644	-1.0069065	-1.0511513	-19.700453	-19.728466	-19.745752	-19.679295	-19.685715	-19.64875	-19.667492
-19.660156	-19.913038	-19.850258	-19.892448	-19.700453	-19.728466	-19.745752	-19.679295	-19.685715	-19.64875	-19.667492
-19.660156	-19.913038	-19.850258	-19.892448	-19.700453	-19.728466	-19.745752	-19.679295	-19.685715	-19.64875	-19.667492
-19.660156	-19.913038	-19.850258	-19.892448	-19.700453	-19.728466	-19.745752	-19.679295	-19.685715	-19.64875	-19.667492
-0.84882164	-1.1833916	-1.1468163	-1.2564831	-19.700453	-19.728466	-19.745752	-19.679295	-19.685715	-19.64875	-19.667492

normalized_BIO+T22_R3_2: Log2	normalized_BIO+T22_R3_3: Log2	normalized_BIO_R1_1: Log2	normalized_BIO_R1_2: Log2	normalized_BIO_R1_3: Log2	normalized_BIO_R2_1: Log2	normalized_BIO_R2_2: Log2	normalized_BIO_R2_3: Log2	normalized_BIO_R3_1: Log2	normalized_BIO_R3_2: Log2	normalized_BIO_R3_3: Log2
2.3705883	2.3538742	2.329403	2.4350243	2.3666496	3.2427864	3.3032932	3.289034	2.1228828	2.1467476	2.148075
2.3512173	2.3219013	2.2863712	2.3866215	2.3303928	2.5981617	2.6453266	2.6481152	2.4963284	2.533144	2.5257683
0.22554016	0.20946312	1.3664017	1.4866886	1.4630089	2.5946693	2.7053738	2.621397	-1.3036842	-1.2675133	-1.3499374
2.5052109	2.4811287	1.9481144	2.038807	1.9541569	2.4551601	2.517376	2.5022545	1.9457874	1.989542	2.0086517
1.7244186	1.7112675	2.479782	2.5869923	2.6060982	3.4056664	3.5330544	3.4347076	1.025465	1.0409336	0.9276638
1.3302898	1.3887997	-1.7131042	-1.662962	-2.2072392	-2.0455265	-1.9011269	-2.4670544	-1.4887409	-1.2620087	-1.3708248
1.1790371	1.1467075	1.5482979	1.43186	1.4945583	1.7826824	1.8534317	1.8193302	1.2522488	1.2473888	1.2785587
0.90927887	0.92414665	0.0	0.16900826	0.0	0.18404007	0.42172813	0.35871696	1.1331882	1.3636112	1.209383
0.35102844	0.26218414	0.42848396	0.3474083	0.47075653	0.37552452	0.43312645	0.43189812	1.3409729	1.3192673	1.3575974
0.0	0.08006668	0.7623062	0.987072	0.94124985	0.8513279	1.1544685	1.1309013	2.0732422	2.1273804	2.1296825
0.39835358	0.35655594	0.32167816	0.5129318	0.38370895	-0.611639	-0.52555275	-0.54673004	-0.18924904	-0.10047722	-0.16722679
-0.28430557	-0.32436752	0.004714966	-0.074892044	0.0262928	-0.03255272	-0.001209259	0.013608932	0.9044609	0.9236851	0.93035126
-19.822626	-19.85958	0.13046265	0.32671928	0.209692	-0.13911629	0.0540123	-0.08780861	0.78385925	0.681406	0.8473072
-19.822626	-19.85958	-0.7749615	-0.74137497	-0.72868156	0.10638046	0.15886688	0.2341938	-0.25756073	-0.22704124	-0.24141884
-19.822626	-19.85958	1.0562286	-0.24328232	-0.271492	0.0	-0.13551712	-0.12235069	0.409235	0.21110535	0.27885056
-0.41348648	-0.40189743	0.10647583	0.13208008	0.14816856	-0.043193817	0.0	0.011676788	-0.15758514	-0.18260765	-0.15568733
0.21719742	0.1993103	0.3029747	0.3905468	0.32601547	0.42983818	0.46306038	0.47348213	0.0	0.0	-0.025627136
0.27861404	0.19791603	-0.022151947	0.1698227	0.17337036	-0.39787483	-0.40353203	-0.3660164	0.41062927	0.4245491	0.44813156
-0.2853012	-0.2160759	-0.5903244	-0.69156265	-0.47952652	-0.96808624	-0.6061344	-0.64328384	0.09165764	0.2200756	0.15886879
-1.2826004	-1.3252392	-0.8627167	-0.7812729	-0.73184395	-0.2888317	-0.15144348	-0.24918747	-1.6840248	-1.7089863	-1.795784
-19.822626	-19.85958	-0.56046295	-0.25681686	-0.42764854	-0.60653687	-0.3126831	-0.7650242	0.14978981	0.26475906	0.2251606
-19.822626	-19.85958	-0.46034622	-0.091459274	-0.30536842	-0.6467476	-0.34051895	-0.5044384	0.25383568	0.3085518	0.33447456
-19.822626	-19.85958	-0.11968422	-1.8561764	-2.0651684	-0.9413471	-1.1256886	-1.1422787	-19.37149	-19.369053	-19.34768
-19.822626	-19.85958	-0.73633957	-0.47724533	-0.7109947	-0.47898865	-0.09284592	-0.18117142	-1.2852402	-1.1688156	-1.2900352
-19.822626	-19.85958	-0.50834846	-0.44776535	-0.5073986	-0.0960598	-0.59318733	-0.11097717	0.27537918	0.057546616	0.019832611
-19.822626	-19.85958	-1.2772598	-0.440382	-0.89515305	-1.3650455	-1.5632381	-0.94545555	-0.3948307	-0.13476944	-0.1938076
-19.822626	-19.85958	0.9836178	1.1734982	0.86888313	1.5931187	1.5087738	1.5211391	-0.38202095	-0.39935112	-0.39800835
-19.822626	-19.85958	-0.20248032	-0.10236359	-0.17662239	0.012245178	0.08441353	-0.13770103	-3.3260517	-3.28331	-3.2338562
-19.822626	-19.85958	-0.43608475	-0.32021904	-0.6291008	-0.20683861	0.123514175	0.0	0.9387989	0.94818497	1.0720596
-2.0701866	-2.0129871	-1.1924248	-1.0914745	-1.296423	-0.508585	-0.627882	-0.63155746	-2.7742233	-2.724844	-2.6626701
-1.9654179	-2.0340118	-2.1347618	-1.7816162	-1.8172607	-0.8158951	-0.49821854	-0.5076637	-4.3632374	-4.065736	-4.5863876
-0.35938454	-0.31970978	-1.3522797	-1.0775719	-1.3246021	-1.123249	-1.0668888	-1.0777473	-1.07716217	-0.10308266	-0.15447807
-19.822626	-19.85958	-1.0988979	-1.2408524	-1.0641117	-0.96201134	-0.9152489	-0.91734314	-0.3279667	-0.38153458	-0.2970295
-19.822626	-19.85958	-0.7063198	-0.65704346	-0.76763153	-0.81391525	-0.8232689	-0.79026794	-0.17696953	-0.15542412	-0.20721626
-1.0348511	-0.97867966	-0.8349228	-0.89063454	-0.7034588	-1.2102184	-1.0304852	-0.9389744	-1.2222996	-0.8849926	-1.167984
-1.654707	-1.6782036	-0.78425026	-0.62734795	-0.70329475	-1.5545368	-1.5117054	-1.506813	-1.6430244	-1.6551285	-1.6217403
-19.822626	-19.85958	-1.3041954	-2.6720066	-2.8630161	-0.7741089	-0.802248	-0.7870636	-0.34942627	-0.48314857	-0.38671494
-19.822626	-19.85958	-1.5407867	-1.2442913	-1.2733803	-1.4341984	-1.2208881	-1.3585415	-0.7528477	-0.5125332	-0.65925217
-0.7389393	-0.74963	-1.0410767	-0.8796654	-0.98099136	-1.0527248	-0.9677315	-0.9687214	-0.31653404	-0.26449966	-0.27472496
-2.466896	-2.5054417	-1.6500492	-1.4850388	-1.631464	-1.0676479	-1.0123959	-1.0081596	-2.0694408	-2.0617886	-2.0069427
-0.59080315	-0.6501217	-1.0112209	-0.6408844	-0.92694664	-0.9565277	-0.994957	-0.9495449	-0.5323734	-0.22367287	-0.1987915
-0.7293167	-0.7153969	-0.903677	-0.79325294	-0.8849869	-1.1675167	-1.1417046	-1.129879	-0.7904453	-0.7893028	-0.7969513
-19.822626	-19.85958	-1.9300346	-1.8573246	-1.9127083	-1.5283566	-1.9779015	-1.527441	-0.9078064	-1.2071381	-1.1832085
-19.822626	-19.85958	-2.5956287	-2.7236366	-2.9597607	-3.2922382	-3.485674	-2.5062237	-4.2222996	-4.1331882	-3.7372599
-1.8713818	-1.9289856	-1.5452251	-1.4530754	-1.5247211	-2.7359848	-2.6298695	-2.6281223	-0.7239132	-0.7435436	-0.71152496
-1.5244999	-1.5545197	-2.824913	-3.2472153	-2.6238556	-1.4289856	-1.2028141	-1.1615334	-2.1222382	-2.2197819	-2.2811794
-2.7532196	-2.7682686	-1.9417095	-1.824522	-3.0189495	-3.2872105	-3.6245327	-1.4647408	-5.385648	-5.2917366	-4.755048

normalized_ BIO+T22_R3 2: Log2	normalized_ BIO+T22_R3 3: Log2	normalized_ BIO_R1_1: L og2	normalized_ BIO_R1_2: L og2	normalized_ BIO_R1_3: L og2	normalized_ BIO_R2_1: L og2	normalized_ BIO_R2_2: L og2	normalized_ BIO_R2_3: L og2	normalized_ BIO_R3_1: L og2	normalized_ BIO_R3_2: L og2	normalized_ BIO_R3_3: L og2
-19.822626	-19.85958	-19.77303	-19.71466	-19.74085	-19.929924	-19.871014	-19.874687	-19.37149	-19.369053	-19.34768
-19.822626	-19.85958	-19.77303	-19.71466	-19.74085	-19.929924	-19.871014	-19.874687	-19.37149	-19.369053	-19.34768
-19.822626	-19.85958	-19.77303	-19.71466	-19.74085	-19.929924	-19.871014	-19.874687	-19.37149	-19.369053	-19.34768
-19.822626	-19.85958	-19.77303	-19.71466	-19.74085	-19.929924	-19.871014	-19.874687	-19.37149	-19.369053	-19.34768
-19.822626	-19.85958	-19.77303	-19.71466	-19.74085	-19.929924	-19.871014	-19.874687	-19.37149	-19.369053	-19.34768

normalized_ C_R1_1: Log 2	normalized_ C_R1_2: Log 2	normalized_ C_R1_3: Log 2	normalized_ C_R2_1: Log 2	normalized_ C_R2_2: Log 2	normalized_ C_R2_3: Log 2	normalized_ C_R3_1: Log 2	normalized_ C_R3_2: Log 2	normalized_ C_R3_3: Log 2	normalized_ T22+76A_R1 1: Log2	normalized_ T22+76A_R1 2: Log2
-19.226398	-19.438581	-19.583866	-19.921492	-19.846977	-19.815422	-19.839325	-19.883402	-19.914055	3.594078	3.7212334
3.497364	3.5197906	3.4356556	2.8157616	2.8779545	2.9351158	3.6251068	3.6298275	3.5849037	2.8171139	2.9370575
-1.0669422	-1.2004108	-1.2637177	0.25211906	0.43827248	0.47286034	1.5607605	1.5435295	1.5073452	-19.990282	-19.868818
-1.1109543	-1.032114	-1.0939255	-0.912508	-0.9587288	-0.7689743	-1.3324566	-1.3677101	-1.4402351	1.3327179	1.4547138
1.1420345	0.9587002	0.8902359	1.7212219	1.9241886	1.9913425	2.6971016	2.663807	2.6231747	-19.990282	-19.868818
1.923254	1.69491	1.7795677	1.6057396	1.6897316	1.819025	1.7574921	1.6268692	1.6773682	1.2274666	1.3301773
-19.226398	-19.438581	-19.583866	-19.921492	-19.846977	-19.815422	-19.839325	-19.883402	-19.914055	-19.990282	-19.868818
-0.7180977	-0.6652489	-0.70970154	-1.5875034	-1.5167465	-0.8589382	-0.9209881	-0.97400093	-1.1142921	0.31061554	0.5255184
0.24648285	0.5268841	0.42798233	-0.2079258	-0.017305374	0.19029427	0.91714287	0.76263237	0.6177826	-19.990282	-19.868818
0.19264793	0.33340073	0.25217056	0.11850357	0.12787247	0.53056335	0.15212631	0.0	0.010940552	-0.4639473	-0.4537239
0.91360474	1.0305061	0.98259544	-0.34519196	-0.22481537	-0.3262043	-0.12799263	-0.04740143	-0.014659882	-19.990282	-19.868818
-0.34921265	-0.044826508	-0.11920738	-0.6827183	-0.52238655	-0.29724884	0.44042587	0.25884247	0.1169796	-19.990282	-19.868818
-19.226398	-19.438581	-19.583866	-19.921492	-19.846977	-19.815422	-19.839325	-19.883402	-19.914055	-19.990282	-19.868818
-19.226398	-19.438581	-19.583866	-19.921492	-19.846977	-19.815422	-19.839325	-19.883402	-19.914055	-19.990282	-19.868818
-19.226398	-19.438581	-19.583866	-19.921492	-19.846977	-19.815422	-19.839325	-19.883402	-19.914055	-19.990282	-19.868818
-0.3322754	-0.044591904	-0.08952904	-0.6842346	-0.6264839	-0.5463104	0.3208599	0.25231934	0.2024746	0.13188934	-0.43058014
-19.226398	-19.438581	-19.583866	0.3077755	0.35805702	0.42839813	-0.4286785	-0.46867943	-0.483284	-0.34840965	-0.26398087
-1.6316586	-2.161049	-1.5738907	-1.864954	-1.4910755	-1.6326218	-1.9462891	-1.9904385	-2.1070328	-19.990282	-19.868818
-19.226398	-19.438581	-19.583866	-19.921492	-19.846977	-19.815422	-19.839325	-19.883402	-19.914055	-19.990282	-19.868818
-1.6062717	-1.7899303	-1.8856087	-1.4014492	-1.166811	-1.1430206	-0.6248188	-0.6856499	-0.722044	-0.25649834	-0.16688156
0.5155239	0.55537415	0.5106354	0.24610138	0.305727	0.30836868	0.028966904	0.091278076	0.23489189	-0.11260605	0.0
-19.226398	-19.438581	-19.583866	-19.921492	-19.846977	-19.815422	-19.839325	-19.883402	-19.914055	-19.990282	-19.868818
-19.226398	-19.438581	-19.583866	-2.9408054	-0.86556816	-2.9793968	-0.20090675	-1.1125317	-1.1989918	-19.990282	-19.868818
0.0	0.16765785	0.1453762	-0.8255081	-0.73971176	-0.8277836	-0.7145691	-0.5585499	-0.4119377	-19.990282	-19.868818
-0.70588493	-0.44096565	-0.44031715	-0.12112236	0.0	0.0	-0.3186264	-0.44568634	-0.39815903	-1.4917717	-1.5442104
0.41081047	0.6020832	0.66480637	0.043907166	0.09049606	-0.08913612	-0.41018295	-0.2315712	0.048484802	-0.72960854	-0.2732563
-19.226398	-19.438581	-19.583866	-19.921492	-19.846977	-19.815422	-19.839325	-19.883402	-19.914055	1.686182	1.8418922
-19.226398	-19.438581	-19.583866	-19.921492	-19.846977	-19.815422	-19.839325	-19.883402	-19.914055	-0.50491905	-0.001367569
-19.226398	-19.438581	-19.583866	-19.921492	-19.846977	-19.815422	-19.839325	-19.883402	-19.914055	-19.990282	-19.868818
-19.226398	-19.438581	-19.583866	-19.921492	-19.846977	-19.815422	-19.839325	-19.883402	-19.914055	-0.2943802	-0.21706581
-19.226398	-19.438581	-19.583866	-19.921492	-19.846977	-19.815422	-19.839325	-19.883402	-19.914055	0.046663284	0.2833557
-0.22429276	-0.11598015	-0.16295242	-0.38007545	-0.32551575	-0.41205597	-0.48975182	-0.433136	-0.416502	-1.0005054	-0.7540455
-19.226398	-19.438581	-19.583866	-19.921492	-19.846977	-19.815422	-19.839325	-19.883402	-19.914055	-19.990282	-19.868818
-19.226398	-19.438581	-19.583866	-19.921492	-19.846977	-19.815422	-19.839325	-19.883402	-19.914055	-1.7159214	-1.6272106
1.2157612	1.1921482	1.1476402	0.85917664	0.8994484	0.93218994	0.35803223	0.32045174	0.28149986	-1.1101189	-2.261612
-19.226398	-19.438581	-19.583866	-19.921492	-19.846977	-19.815422	-19.839325	-19.883402	-19.914055	-1.3640785	-1.1569328
-19.226398	-19.438581	-19.583866	-19.921492	-19.846977	-19.815422	-19.839325	-19.883402	-19.914055	-19.990282	-19.868818
-19.226398	-19.438581	-19.583866	-19.921492	-19.846977	-19.815422	-19.839325	-19.883402	-19.914055	-19.990282	-19.868818
-0.44962883	-0.43570328	-0.46060562	-0.7991295	-0.73965263	-0.80166054	-0.8606167	-0.78508186	-0.82190514	-19.990282	-19.868818
0.95801735	0.96870995	0.91381264	1.4025478	1.5220203	1.5565834	1.967329	1.9066219	1.874773	1.9032555	1.9715309
-19.226398	-0.8013973	-0.72431946	-1.4796581	-1.2729263	-1.3229237	-0.846962	-1.0483627	-0.8267002	-19.990282	-19.868818
-0.48139763	-0.53347206	-0.5964031	-0.5407715	-0.4688244	-0.47758484	-1.0853481	-1.0498905	-1.1191788	-19.990282	-19.868818
-19.226398	-19.438581	-19.583866	-19.921492	-19.846977	-19.815422	-19.839325	-19.883402	-19.914055	-19.990282	-19.868818
-19.226398	-19.438581	-19.583866	-19.921492	-19.846977	-19.815422	-19.839325	-19.883402	-19.914055	-0.8515301	-0.71626854
-0.875618	-0.99853516	-1.0980473	-2.5219383	-2.3782501	-2.4914875	-2.298153	-2.3134956	-2.3702755	-19.990282	-19.868818
-2.2808857	-2.430973	-2.5270157	-1.9468975	-1.8791599	-1.4140549	-0.8924389	-1.012989	-1.0119362	-1.6498795	-1.5549355
-19.226398	-19.438581	-19.583866	-19.921492	-19.846977	-19.815422	-19.839325	-19.883402	-19.914055	-1.5484028	-1.0703526

normalized_ C_R1_1: Log 2	normalized_ C_R1_2: Log 2	normalized_ C_R1_3: Log 2	normalized_ C_R2_1: Log 2	normalized_ C_R2_2: Log 2	normalized_ C_R2_3: Log 2	normalized_ C_R3_1: Log 2	normalized_ C_R3_2: Log 2	normalized_ C_R3_3: Log 2	normalized_ T22+76A_R1 1: Log2	normalized_ T22+76A_R1 2: Log2
-1.3722172	-1.453762	-1.5584011	-1.3632278	-1.3328285	-1.3204021	-1.3477345	-1.292654	-1.3164825	-1.4165306	-1.1928692
-0.85912895	-0.8553295	-0.95578766	-1.3526821	-1.2601299	-1.2533627	-1.7118702	-1.686863	-1.6851234	-19.990282	-19.868818
-2.0465374	-1.2438145	-1.2859154	-2.2962036	-3.25395	-3.3749428	-3.010172	-2.6486683	-2.686617	-2.4615536	-2.1605492
-19.226398	-19.438581	-19.583866	-19.921492	-19.846977	-19.815422	-19.839325	-19.883402	-19.914055	-19.990282	-19.868818
1.0511837	1.1027699	0.93689156	0.5776577	0.69524956	0.5951824	0.55319786	0.6263523	0.8598652	-19.990282	-19.868818
1.267458	1.3727646	1.2981606	2.0727825	2.1053753	2.1857147	2.3881645	2.336277	2.2972717	-19.990282	-19.868818
-19.226398	-19.438581	-19.583866	-19.921492	-19.846977	-19.815422	-19.839325	-19.883402	-19.914055	0.9731903	1.0290775
-1.0646706	-1.2848663	-1.3571205	-0.91087914	-0.64964294	-0.6595764	-0.13060951	-0.19537926	-0.18862915	0.2747097	0.35554314
-19.226398	-19.438581	-19.583866	-19.921492	-19.846977	-19.815422	-19.839325	-19.883402	-19.914055	-19.990282	-19.868818
-19.226398	-19.438581	-19.583866	-19.921492	-19.846977	-19.815422	-19.839325	-19.883402	-19.914055	-19.990282	-19.868818
-19.226398	-19.438581	-19.583866	-19.921492	-19.846977	-19.815422	-19.839325	-19.883402	-19.914055	0.097717285	0.39365196
-19.226398	-19.438581	-19.583866	-0.54442596	-0.42393875	-0.29795837	-0.10151291	-0.2520504	-0.32650185	-19.990282	-19.868818
-0.9520798	-1.6397305	-1.7982788	-1.7541618	-2.553587	-1.5024776	-1.7403793	-1.9769115	-2.3087711	-19.990282	-19.868818
-19.226398	-19.438581	-19.583866	-19.921492	-19.846977	-19.815422	-19.839325	-19.883402	-19.914055	0.10199356	0.30236626
-0.23436737	0.0	-0.21682358	-0.66231537	-0.508955	-0.8629284	-0.90385246	-0.93276787	-0.7801895	-0.98195267	-0.4919014
-0.31913757	-0.016702652	0.0	-0.18361473	-0.2371769	-0.36400986	-0.4261284	-0.1984787	-0.004121780	-0.649868	-0.306839
-0.9841366	-1.1199551	-1.197052	-1.9145241	-1.7566128	-1.7539673	-1.5608025	-1.6446571	-1.5197258	-19.990282	-19.868818
-19.226398	-19.438581	-19.583866	-19.921492	-19.846977	-19.815422	-19.839325	-19.883402	-19.914055	-19.990282	-19.868818
-0.4142723	-0.45905685	-0.5398426	-1.3005676	-1.2312145	-1.2764797	-1.1530228	-1.1369343	-1.147829	-19.990282	-19.868818
-0.97130585	-0.88497925	-0.96185684	-1.1310406	-1.064085	-1.0782108	-1.2493935	-1.2868919	-1.3091831	-19.990282	-19.868818
-19.226398	-19.438581	-19.583866	-19.921492	-19.846977	-19.815422	-19.839325	-19.883402	-19.914055	-1.5085144	-1.64077
-19.226398	-19.438581	-19.583866	-19.921492	-19.846977	-19.815422	-19.839325	-19.883402	-19.914055	-19.990282	-19.868818
-19.226398	-19.438581	-19.583866	-19.921492	-19.846977	-19.815422	-19.839325	-19.883402	-19.914055	-19.990282	-19.868818
-1.2912807	-1.0632248	-1.338522	-1.6681843	-1.9788609	-1.9811859	-2.1877956	-2.0186481	-1.6976585	-2.010929	-1.618742
-19.226398	-19.438581	-19.583866	-19.921492	-19.846977	-19.815422	-19.839325	-19.883402	-19.914055	-19.990282	-19.868818
-19.226398	-19.438581	-19.583866	-19.921492	-19.846977	-19.815422	-19.839325	-19.883402	-19.914055	2.8040524	2.9314747
-19.226398	-19.438581	-19.583866	-19.921492	-19.846977	-19.815422	-19.839325	-19.883402	-19.914055	0.95269394	1.0821724
-19.226398	-19.438581	-19.583866	-19.921492	-19.846977	-19.815422	-19.839325	-19.883402	-19.914055	1.7100163	1.8323154
-19.226398	-19.438581	-19.583866	-19.921492	-19.846977	-19.815422	-19.839325	-19.883402	-19.914055	-0.9884758	-0.5924034
-19.226398	-19.438581	-19.583866	-19.921492	-19.846977	-19.815422	-19.839325	-19.883402	-19.914055	0.5758991	0.60726166
-19.226398	-19.438581	-19.583866	-19.921492	-19.846977	-19.815422	-19.839325	-19.883402	-19.914055	-0.66059494	-0.7573128
-19.226398	-19.438581	-19.583866	-19.921492	-19.846977	-19.815422	-19.839325	-19.883402	-19.914055	-1.2715645	-1.2887917
-19.226398	-19.438581	-19.583866	-19.921492	-19.846977	-19.815422	-19.839325	-19.883402	-19.914055	1.8098869	1.902914
-19.226398	-19.438581	-19.583866	-19.921492	-19.846977	-19.815422	-19.839325	-19.883402	-19.914055	-1.9233265	-1.7542477
0.11164284	-0.16802216	0.118061066	0.03705597	-0.23305893	-0.4643612	-0.2710266	-0.13805771	-0.001905441	0.0	-0.050857544
-19.226398	-19.438581	-19.583866	-19.921492	-19.846977	-19.815422	-19.839325	-19.883402	-19.914055	-1.0536804	-0.93494034
-0.58322525	-0.64501	-0.719614	-1.3737392	-1.310051	-1.3099937	-0.8575344	-0.85746	-0.87127686	-0.6443825	-0.5394268
-19.226398	-19.438581	-19.583866	-19.921492	-19.846977	-19.815422	-19.839325	-19.883402	-19.914055	-0.32383728	2.4604797E-4
-19.226398	-19.438581	-19.583866	-19.921492	-19.846977	-19.815422	-19.839325	-19.883402	-19.914055	-19.990282	-19.868818
-19.226398	-19.438581	-19.583866	-19.921492	-19.846977	-19.815422	-19.839325	-19.883402	-19.914055	-19.990282	-19.868818
-19.226398	-19.438581	-19.583866	-19.921492	-19.846977	-19.815422	-19.839325	-19.883402	-19.914055	-19.990282	-19.868818
-19.226398	-19.438581	-19.583866	-19.921492	-19.846977	-19.815422	-19.839325	-19.883402	-19.914055	-19.990282	-19.868818
-19.226398	-19.438581	-19.583866	-19.921492	-19.846977	-19.815422	-19.839325	-19.883402	-19.914055	-19.990282	-19.868818
-19.226398	-19.438581	-19.583866	-19.921492	-19.846977	-19.815422	-19.839325	-19.883402	-19.914055	-19.990282	-19.868818
-19.226398	-19.438581	-19.583866	-19.921492	-19.846977	-19.815422	-19.839325	-19.883402	-19.914055	-19.990282	-19.868818
-1.5196056	-1.5542564	-1.6394501	-2.0967503	-2.0558338	-2.1058674	-1.694128	-1.6697903	-1.6503868	-19.990282	-19.868818
-19.226398	-19.438581	-19.583866	-19.921492	-19.846977	-19.815422	-19.839325	-19.883402	-19.914055	-19.990282	-19.868818
-1.7495651	-1.7376614	-1.8166637	-0.7370796	-0.61465454	-0.5608597	-1.8730946	-1.8966427	-1.9237404	-19.990282	-19.868818

normalized_ C_R1_1: Log 2	normalized_ C_R1_2: Log 2	normalized_ C_R1_3: Log 2	normalized_ C_R2_1: Log 2	normalized_ C_R2_2: Log 2	normalized_ C_R2_3: Log 2	normalized_ C_R3_1: Log 2	normalized_ C_R3_2: Log 2	normalized_ C_R3_3: Log 2	normalized_T 22+76A_R1_1 : Log2	normalized_T 22+76A_R1_2 : Log2
-0.7329216	-0.6720238	-0.6880932	-0.83633804	-0.821352	-0.6568279	-1.2055244	-1.3522186	-1.3474102	-19.990282	-19.868818
-19.226398	-19.438581	-19.583866	-19.921492	-19.846977	-19.815422	-19.839325	-19.883402	-19.914055	-19.990282	-19.868818
2.7711258	2.7507515	2.6335907	2.3657131	2.5101147	2.5223255	2.2529602	2.234026	2.1926804	-19.990282	-19.868818
-19.226398	-19.438581	-19.583866	-19.921492	-19.846977	-19.815422	-19.839325	-19.883402	-19.914055	-19.990282	-19.868818
-19.226398	-19.438581	-19.583866	-19.921492	-19.846977	-19.815422	-19.839325	-19.883402	-19.914055	-19.990282	-19.868818

normalized_T22+76A_R1_3: Log2	normalized_T22+76A_R2_1: Log2	normalized_T22+76A_R2_2: Log2	normalized_T22+76A_R2_3: Log2	normalized_T22+76A_R3_1: Log2	normalized_T22+76A_R3_2: Log2	normalized_T22+76A_R3_3: Log2	normalized_T22_R1_1: Log2	normalized_T22_R1_2: Log2	normalized_T22_R1_3: Log2	normalized_T22_R2_1: Log2
3.6481552	3.48905	3.4602757	3.6210155	2.9290638	2.74687	2.8938465	0.70588493	0.7120781	0.73719406	2.6718445
2.850319	2.8643875	2.8523655	2.9652557	2.7117977	2.5760345	2.6880302	1.7463741	1.7023659	1.7774067	2.5030975
-19.941566	-19.868841	-19.890398	-19.710253	-19.653141	-19.879122	-19.693626	-2.3764763	-2.4496155	-2.337225	1.153101
1.3717213	2.2884579	2.2543488	2.4210682	2.0428638	1.9855633	2.1415138	2.6866322	2.6452446	2.7121983	1.7334538
-19.941566	-19.868841	-19.890398	-19.710253	-19.653141	-19.879122	-19.693626	0.23039246	0.17733765	0.25194168	2.4098778
1.3545761	1.5558376	1.5533028	1.7157459	1.6385689	1.6430798	1.5109959	1.7638493	1.7955036	1.6995983	1.7212467
-19.941566	-19.868841	-19.890398	-19.710253	-19.653141	-19.879122	-19.693626	1.0513229	1.0772877	1.0481014	1.9122276
0.43959236	0.8286495	0.8816776	0.8281555	0.8476982	0.794466	0.60040665	0.7172642	0.41148758	0.82777023	0.7530365
-19.941566	-19.868841	-19.890398	-19.710253	-19.653141	-19.879122	-19.693626	-0.14356232	0.13903809	-0.008602142	0.76937866
-0.54486465	-0.052417755	-0.16399574	-0.013870239	-0.15050125	-0.14361572	0.11906433	0.40921783	0.37156487	0.41972733	0.36662674
-19.941566	-19.868841	-19.890398	-19.710253	-19.653141	-19.879122	-19.693626	0.4548645	0.29945755	0.4042549	-0.16821289
-19.941566	-19.868841	-19.890398	-19.710253	-19.653141	-19.879122	-19.693626	-0.6816025	-0.39727974	-0.52363586	0.30603218
-19.941566	-19.868841	-19.890398	-19.710253	-19.653141	-19.879122	-19.693626	0.6545105	0.40285683	0.54001045	0.31040192
-19.941566	-19.868841	-19.890398	-19.710253	-19.653141	-19.879122	-19.693626	-19.563974	-19.577085	-19.542694	-19.757208
-19.941566	-19.868841	-19.890398	-19.710253	-19.653141	-19.879122	-19.693626	-19.563974	-19.577085	-19.542694	-19.757208
0.16348839	-0.40512657	-0.43057823	-0.21166801	-0.30006218	-0.5129833	-0.21186447	-1.4668427	-1.4135399	-1.432272	0.020198822
-0.3326683	-0.10075188	-0.18101883	-0.044563293	-0.25739098	-0.4373665	-0.2620983	1.0244198	1.0151691	1.0660744	0.0
-19.941566	-19.868841	-19.890398	-19.710253	-19.653141	-19.879122	-19.693626	-0.52082634	-0.53077126	-0.43894768	-1.1868668
-19.941566	-19.868841	-19.890398	-19.710253	-19.653141	-19.879122	-19.693626	-0.56666183	-0.5601444	-0.13728714	-0.75746155
-0.20998764	-0.20801735	-0.14124489	-0.031570435	-0.5472851	-0.7579441	-0.6260166	-2.4100857	-2.5031433	-2.3907948	-0.822443
0.0528183	0.27784538	0.26210785	0.22159195	0.20696259	0.18021774	0.2805004	0.001934051	-0.17745018	-0.031663895	-0.33483887
-19.941566	-19.868841	-19.890398	-19.710253	-19.653141	-19.879122	-19.693626	0.0	0.334795	0.4641323	-0.23556519
-19.941566	-19.868841	-19.890398	-19.710253	-19.653141	-19.879122	-19.693626	0.3483963	0.04620552	-0.3384037	-0.5079155
-19.941566	-19.868841	-19.890398	-19.710253	-19.653141	-19.879122	-19.693626	-19.563974	-19.577085	-19.542694	-19.757208
-1.5849934	-0.47140884	-0.58010674	-0.72465897	-0.45712662	-0.9316387	-0.39782715	-19.563974	-19.577085	-19.542694	-19.757208
-0.36472702	-0.0704689	-0.06326485	-0.20827675	-0.06651497	0.14692879	-0.28484535	-0.19296265	-0.32500267	-0.24775887	-0.02400589
1.527111	1.3017273	1.5409298	1.7242718	0.8134804	0.6118851	1.0063057	-0.5796356	-0.23186111	-0.47007942	1.0165005
-0.04975128	-0.41263962	-0.46637344	-0.31364822	-1.3283272	-1.4479961	-1.337019	-19.563974	-19.577085	-19.542694	-19.757208
-19.941566	-19.868841	-19.890398	-19.710253	-19.653141	-19.879122	-19.693626	-19.563974	-19.577085	-19.542694	-19.757208
-0.35289	-0.8960495	-0.89621353	-0.63490486	-1.552084	-1.8356514	-1.1084499	-3.7447186	-3.705349	-3.694193	-1.3772755
0.24926758	0.0	-0.024475098	-0.033506393	-0.7770767	-0.8046112	-1.5326862	-5.4904184	-6.647457	-6.275176	-2.1281147
-0.8585224	-0.4440136	-0.63705254	-0.6910114	-0.512722	-0.3318138	-0.83350754	-1.944006	-1.8386631	-1.9414749	-2.3289452
-19.941566	-19.868841	-19.890398	-19.710253	-19.653141	-19.879122	-19.693626	-19.563974	-19.577085	-19.542694	-19.757208
-1.6644516	-0.48789215	-0.5603676	-0.45573425	-0.28191376	-0.4249363	-0.2849598	-0.66729355	-0.6984234	-0.6087074	-1.154499
-2.4955902	-1.0836239	-2.1377754	-1.92519	-0.8344307	-1.6986637	-1.7771187	0.8424721	0.8541622	0.76335716	-0.31059647
-1.2879238	-1.7447605	-1.7701302	-1.6507092	-0.663126	-0.7549095	-0.69861794	-1.0452061	-1.10326	-1.0060291	-1.863718
-19.941566	-19.868841	-19.890398	-19.710253	-19.653141	-19.879122	-19.693626	-0.870039	-0.93136406	-0.90159035	-1.7306786
-19.941566	-19.868841	-19.890398	-19.710253	-19.653141	-19.879122	-19.693626	-19.563974	-19.577085	-19.542694	-19.757208
-19.941566	-19.868841	-19.890398	-19.710253	-19.653141	-19.879122	-19.693626	-0.39494705	-0.49858093	-0.3328266	-0.9118614
1.9758015	1.7139587	1.6890144	1.8285236	1.5599537	1.3891582	1.6324787	-2.3223553	-2.3863926	-2.2711487	-1.4032555
-19.941566	-19.868841	-19.890398	-19.710253	-19.653141	-19.879122	-19.693626	-1.0861931	-1.0922298	-0.9909401	-1.0812244
-19.941566	-19.868841	-19.890398	-19.710253	-19.653141	-19.879122	-19.693626	-19.563974	-19.577085	-19.542694	-19.757208
-19.941566	-19.868841	-19.890398	-19.710253	-19.653141	-19.879122	-19.693626	-1.2574196	-1.3436165	-1.2336979	-2.0328999
-0.8273945	-0.9706726	-0.99025345	-0.80353546	-1.6705589	-1.8372116	-1.576086	-19.563974	-19.577085	-19.542694	-19.757208
-19.941566	-19.868841	-19.890398	-19.710253	-19.653141	-19.879122	-19.693626	-1.3109856	-1.3129501	-1.2714825	-1.7634468
-1.537035	-1.015583	-1.1233673	-1.0310001	-1.558733	-1.8896503	-1.5383434	-3.801074	-3.605564	-3.846922	-1.5430317
-0.75261116	-1.1304817	-2.0353775	-0.9298382	-2.9612198	-2.7901173	-3.2395515	-19.563974	-19.577085	-19.542694	-19.757208

normalized_T22+76A_R1_3: Log2	normalized_T22+76A_R2_1: Log2	normalized_T22+76A_R2_2: Log2	normalized_T22+76A_R2_3: Log2	normalized_T22+76A_R3_1: Log2	normalized_T22+76A_R3_2: Log2	normalized_T22+76A_R3_3: Log2	normalized_T22_R1_1: Log2	normalized_T22_R1_2: Log2	normalized_T22_R1_3: Log2	normalized_T22_R2_1: Log2
-1.3271198	-1.4354057	-1.4362831	-1.3203526	-1.5051804	-1.563034	-1.5466442	-19.563974	-19.577085	-19.542694	-19.757208
-19.941566	-19.868841	-19.890398	-19.710253	-19.653141	-19.879122	-19.693626	-0.7120609	-0.7710304	-0.69525146	-2.0036907
-2.2760086	-2.532631	-3.048809	-2.6950226	-2.9289608	-2.953497	-3.379221	-2.3274002	-2.6855278	-2.3765411	-3.5246181
-19.941566	-19.868841	-19.890398	-19.710253	-19.653141	-19.879122	-19.693626	-1.9634743	-1.8317127	-1.8434277	-2.374466
-19.941566	-19.868841	-19.890398	-19.710253	-19.653141	-19.879122	-19.693626	-2.4765015	-2.8640213	-2.8377228	-3.3419132
-19.941566	-19.868841	-19.890398	-19.710253	-19.653141	-19.879122	-19.693626	-19.563974	-19.577085	-19.542694	-19.757208
0.9613209	0.8670635	0.79738426	1.1195755	1.0953407	0.7227936	1.206131	-19.563974	-19.577085	-19.542694	-19.757208
0.31793594	0.33327103	0.40670776	0.4981842	-0.057662964	-0.2421093	-0.09974289	-1.8208828	-1.9331455	-1.8517284	-0.27405167
-19.941566	-19.868841	-19.890398	-19.710253	-19.653141	-19.879122	-19.693626	-19.563974	-19.577085	-19.542694	-19.757208
-19.941566	-19.868841	-19.890398	-19.710253	-19.653141	-19.879122	-19.693626	-19.563974	-19.577085	-19.542694	-19.757208
0.13419342	-0.32159805	-0.12078667	-0.23735237	-0.486454	-0.6324825	-0.760849	-19.563974	-19.577085	-19.542694	-19.757208
-19.941566	-19.868841	-19.890398	-19.710253	-19.653141	-19.879122	-19.693626	-19.563974	-19.577085	-19.542694	-19.757208
-19.941566	-19.868841	-19.890398	-19.710253	-19.653141	-19.879122	-19.693626	-19.563974	-19.577085	-19.542694	-19.757208
0.22806549	-0.759573	-0.7952099	-0.7623215	0.5475006	0.45464897	0.3391075	-19.563974	-19.577085	-19.542694	-19.757208
-0.55646706	-0.74843407	-0.4038906	-0.39704323	-0.6677246	-0.475605	-1.0645657	-0.69408226	-1.1957169	-1.0130844	-0.95913124
-0.40099144	-0.117975235	-0.12750626	-0.40548897	-0.11487961	0.0	-0.4473076	-0.06967735	-0.36127472	-0.20257568	-0.2790928
-19.941566	-19.868841	-19.890398	-19.710253	-19.653141	-19.879122	-19.693626	-1.2891235	-1.459589	-1.2729511	-1.50733
-19.941566	-19.868841	-19.890398	-19.710253	-19.653141	-19.879122	-19.693626	-19.563974	-19.577085	-19.542694	-19.757208
-19.941566	-19.868841	-19.890398	-19.710253	-19.653141	-19.879122	-19.693626	-0.84309006	-0.97109604	-0.88030815	-1.5436001
-19.941566	-19.868841	-19.890398	-19.710253	-19.653141	-19.879122	-19.693626	-19.563974	-19.577085	-19.542694	-19.757208
-1.6339207	-2.0464516	-1.8722153	-1.5049572	-1.6441383	-2.2261505	-1.5173607	-19.563974	-19.577085	-19.542694	-19.757208
-19.941566	-19.868841	-19.890398	-19.710253	-19.653141	-19.879122	-19.693626	-19.563974	-19.577085	-19.542694	-19.757208
-19.941566	-19.868841	-19.890398	-19.710253	-19.653141	-19.879122	-19.693626	-19.563974	-19.577085	-19.542694	-19.757208
-1.7503719	-1.3652763	-1.4853191	-1.8339939	-1.4299736	-1.4100056	-2.332325	-2.0053444	-2.066885	-1.6422634	-1.9221325
-19.941566	-19.868841	-19.890398	-19.710253	-19.653141	-19.879122	-19.693626	-19.563974	-19.577085	-19.542694	-19.757208
2.8558903	2.7397003	2.8179417	2.9240227	1.4886055	1.325285	1.4300365	-19.563974	-19.577085	-19.542694	-19.757208
1.009964	0.8803158	0.9714718	1.0647526	-0.367054	-0.5432472	-0.42607117	-19.563974	-19.577085	-19.542694	-19.757208
1.7353935	1.1474228	1.1144409	1.2876625	0.3929577	0.35199738	0.5737953	-19.563974	-19.577085	-19.542694	-19.757208
-0.7925911	-0.80252457	-1.4190884	-1.0004826	-1.9324493	-2.4224472	-1.7527122	-1.5631771	-1.713438	-1.4755707	-1.0984268
0.5266838	0.43903732	0.38205528	0.7020321	0.6795826	0.31813622	0.7806988	-19.563974	-19.577085	-19.542694	-19.757208
-0.81588554	-0.88690186	-0.999979	-0.54276085	-0.97400093	-1.1138878	-0.91418266	-19.563974	-19.577085	-19.542694	-19.757208
-1.253603	-1.1349258	-1.147131	-1.0685501	-1.750536	-1.5747528	-1.1430073	-19.563974	-19.577085	-19.542694	-19.757208
1.8312931	1.3843727	1.3591709	1.5670986	1.2271786	0.99840736	1.2745304	-19.563974	-19.577085	-19.542694	-19.757208
-1.7219543	-1.9490337	-1.5665474	-1.1377201	-1.7498474	-1.6793308	-1.5179844	-19.563974	-19.577085	-19.542694	-19.757208
-0.43527412	-0.039993286	0.0	-0.045215607	0.0	0.049791336	-0.41222382	-19.563974	-19.577085	-19.542694	-19.757208
-0.9715843	-1.5935402	-1.61516	-1.4626808	-2.2877083	-2.4219341	-2.3069553	-19.563974	-19.577085	-19.542694	-19.757208
-0.6000385	-0.5772934	-0.5913124	-0.42294312	-0.77690506	-0.9020176	-0.7511406	-19.563974	-19.577085	-19.542694	-19.757208
-0.13492012	-0.611166	-0.58600044	-0.70111275	-0.89809227	-1.4003716	-1.3428383	-19.563974	-19.577085	-19.542694	-19.757208
-19.941566	-19.868841	-19.890398	-19.710253	-19.653141	-19.879122	-19.693626	-19.563974	-19.577085	-19.542694	-19.757208
-19.941566	-19.868841	-19.890398	-19.710253	-19.653141	-19.879122	-19.693626	-0.15172386	-0.3605194	-0.2473011	-1.3888302
-19.941566	-19.868841	-19.890398	-19.710253	-19.653141	-19.879122	-19.693626	-19.563974	-19.577085	-19.542694	-19.757208
-19.941566	-19.868841	-19.890398	-19.710253	-19.653141	-19.879122	-19.693626	-0.7499962	-0.507988	-0.6792469	-0.53058434
-19.941566	-19.868841	-19.890398	-19.710253	-19.653141	-19.879122	-19.693626	-1.1132908	-1.2552624	-1.1514168	-1.5118179
-19.941566	-19.868841	-19.890398	-19.710253	-19.653141	-19.879122	-19.693626	-19.563974	-19.577085	-19.542694	-19.757208
-19.941566	-19.868841	-19.890398	-19.710253	-19.653141	-19.879122	-19.693626	-19.563974	-19.577085	-19.542694	-19.757208
-19.941566	-19.868841	-19.890398	-19.710253	-19.653141	-19.879122	-19.693626	-19.563974	-19.577085	-19.542694	-19.757208

normalized_T 22+76A_R1_3 : Log2	normalized_T 22+76A_R2_1 : Log2	normalized_T 22+76A_R2_2 : Log2	normalized_T 22+76A_R2_3 : Log2	normalized_T 22+76A_R3_1 : Log2	normalized_T 22+76A_R3_2 : Log2	normalized_T 22+76A_R3_3 : Log2	normalized_T 22_R1_1: Log 2	normalized_T 22_R1_2: Log 2	normalized_T 22_R1_3: Log 2	normalized_T 22_R2_1: Log 2
-19.941566	-19.868841	-19.890398	-19.710253	-19.653141	-19.879122	-19.693626	-19.563974	-19.577085	-19.542694	-19.757208
-19.941566	-19.868841	-19.890398	-19.710253	-19.653141	-19.879122	-19.693626	-19.563974	-19.577085	-19.542694	-19.757208
-19.941566	-19.868841	-19.890398	-19.710253	-19.653141	-19.879122	-19.693626	-19.563974	-19.577085	-19.542694	-19.757208
-19.941566	-19.868841	-19.890398	-19.710253	-19.653141	-19.879122	-19.693626	-19.563974	-19.577085	-19.542694	-19.757208
-19.941566	-19.868841	-19.890398	-19.710253	-19.653141	-19.879122	-19.693626	-19.563974	-19.577085	-19.542694	-19.757208

normalized_T22_R2_2: Log2	normalized_T22_R2_3: Log2	normalized_T22_R3_1: Log2	normalized_T22_R3_2: Log2	normalized_T22_R3_3: Log2	raw_6PP_R1_1	raw_6PP_R1_2	raw_6PP_R1_3	raw_6PP_R2_1	raw_6PP_R2_2	raw_6PP_R2_3
2.701624	2.6991768	2.716961	2.8913612	2.9003582	979416.0	996020.0	995938.0	3820022.0	3859622.0	3849668.0
2.5468578	2.5119038	2.5369816	2.6634808	2.7040253	3110815.0	3093934.0	3041843.0	6836680.0	6902733.0	6915410.0
1.1968975	1.1468945	0.73978806	0.93143463	1.0235405	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
1.74329	1.7503529	2.413124	2.5980015	2.614006	3901457.0	3844074.0	3825707.0	4016430.0	4000142.0	4044636.0
2.4423733	2.3808975	2.0505447	2.2484093	2.3505707	648567.0	542938.0	609055.0	3910522.0	3944744.0	3994848.0
1.9780865	1.8763428	1.5727768	1.5873241	1.6355343	2573771.0	2494483.0	2651954.0	1840141.0	1883351.0	1936663.0
1.9139233	1.9550476	1.1904087	1.376543	1.3878098	1161972.0	1090999.0	1110273.0	2432713.0	2219962.0	2367541.0
0.5726185	0.52293015	0.4717369	0.5390396	0.6540756	382757.0	305040.0	453962.0	306756.0	290480.0	313238.0
0.6965008	0.8536682	0.59793854	0.94786453	0.87073517	752216.0	763250.0	840901.0	878652.0	819853.0	734276.0
0.47459602	0.008752823	-0.3198948	0.06599426	-4.2152405E-	622996.0	676631.0	685552.0	535573.0	480391.0	571756.0
-0.10968971	-0.2096157	0.16668129	0.22912407	0.27495384	688853.0	689039.0	666465.0	681049.0	718819.0	734215.0
0.23080063	0.39658356	0.11408043	0.49777412	0.4060936	563845.0	568185.0	626555.0	654833.0	608519.0	542105.0
0.31285095	0.33405113	0.2383709	0.003091812	0.2833252	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
-19.75276	-19.745102	-20.058607	-19.87998	-19.850355	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
-19.75276	-19.745102	-20.058607	-19.87998	-19.850355	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
0.0	0.030014038	-0.3379097	-0.11845207	-0.1608429	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
-0.014245987	0.015611649	-0.6155491	-0.46305275	-0.45780373	1241549.0	1245437.0	1212599.0	1041509.0	995307.0	1019297.0
-1.2120152	-1.2574177	-1.7764282	-1.6582947	-1.6063766	1371048.0	1331523.0	1346710.0	988563.0	976911.0	959104.0
-0.7931061	-0.63074493	-0.5338993	-0.73646545	-0.82808685	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
-0.8064728	-0.8702736	-1.1180534	-0.9436798	-0.83086777	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
-0.09166336	-0.092990875	-0.05678749	-0.27429962	0.056077957	1056644.0	1140924.0	1033073.0	977267.0	995239.0	1056865.0
-0.022304535	-0.5610962	0.029184341	-0.30026245	-0.11925316	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
-0.34972572	-0.32971	-20.058607	-19.87998	-19.850355	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
-19.75276	-19.745102	-20.058607	-19.87998	-19.850355	373719.0	361494.0	338088.0	661578.0	713902.0	780697.0
-19.75276	-19.745102	-20.058607	-19.87998	-19.850355	593832.0	527001.0	523452.0	434228.0	329573.0	382077.0
0.03966713	-0.2656231	0.0	-0.5707798	0.0	1078091.0	1078142.0	949530.0	766664.0	820103.0	940758.0
0.9936123	1.0147781	0.34331512	0.6318054	0.4922428	535146.0	541057.0	496014.0	1903481.0	1602848.0	1587180.0
-19.75276	-19.745102	-20.058607	-19.87998	-19.850355	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
-19.75276	-19.745102	-20.058607	-19.87998	-19.850355	55994.0	51416.0	106879.0	92890.0	87354.0	116354.0
-1.4502106	-1.3284073	-1.774044	-1.2832603	-1.6404076	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
-1.7879734	-2.1612186	-1.1056824	-1.3621864	-0.88067627	15712.0	17138.0	12796.0	124268.0	166167.0	203739.0
-2.6263676	-2.2347393	-2.4797554	-2.041441	-2.256956	488066.0	510612.0	452902.0	345649.0	361318.0	390968.0
-19.75276	-19.745102	-20.058607	-19.87998	-19.850355	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
-1.1634121	-1.1514149	-0.43580818	-0.25897026	-0.27722168	516294.0	496893.0	477871.0	326018.0	324925.0	328339.0
-0.13561058	-0.089365005	-0.41744995	-0.25608635	-0.08419037	744299.0	708536.0	686560.0	539212.0	588803.0	574001.0
-1.8142319	-1.8289719	-0.78253937	-0.60569763	-0.5419979	353891.0	347403.0	360448.0	370404.0	366598.0	379725.0
-1.7192402	-1.7180004	-0.7848053	-0.7199364	-0.67334366	436761.0	419687.0	407405.0	269134.0	262752.0	253018.0
-19.75276	-19.745102	-20.058607	-19.87998	-19.850355	677718.0	403666.0	642002.0	529842.0	435328.0	423962.0
-0.8433857	-0.9256439	-0.7630825	-0.66108894	-0.57127	567385.0	549972.0	560994.0	426341.0	449134.0	460064.0
-1.350977	-1.3174038	-1.6617928	-1.4771595	-1.3388348	101125.0	87362.0	91274.0	356080.0	376710.0	398505.0
-1.1501942	-0.8782978	-1.0199852	-0.8263054	-1.0870094	461024.0	435253.0	452057.0	438275.0	551701.0	574785.0
-19.75276	-19.745102	-20.058607	-19.87998	-19.850355	750464.0	744216.0	740016.0	531325.0	543382.0	553913.0
-2.0818748	-2.139145	-1.3914623	-1.3599796	-1.5125637	333800.0	284446.0	288999.0	181346.0	150231.0	165871.0
-19.75276	-19.745102	-20.058607	-19.87998	-19.850355	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
-1.8332329	-1.7953091	-1.3825569	-1.2231197	-1.2440872	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
-1.6355019	-1.7932262	-1.9598045	-1.9068928	-1.857914	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
-19.75276	-19.745102	-20.058607	-19.87998	-19.850355	39493.0	53674.0	43103.0	206469.0	301015.0	355741.0

normalized_T22_R2_2: Log2	normalized_T22_R2_3: Log2	normalized_T22_R3_1: Log2	normalized_T22_R3_2: Log2	normalized_T22_R3_3: Log2	raw_6PP_R1_1	raw_6PP_R1_2	raw_6PP_R1_3	raw_6PP_R2_1	raw_6PP_R2_2	raw_6PP_R2_3
-19.75276	-19.745102	-20.058607	-19.87998	-19.850355	282593.0	290008.0	275206.0	354389.0	361274.0	372964.0
-1.954382	-2.0440388	-1.6582985	-1.5424423	-1.4836273	369131.0	358147.0	357275.0	269861.0	276718.0	279825.0
-3.2361069	-3.0180454	-2.3236523	-2.6976528	-2.6845455	171392.0	237082.0	204352.0	190129.0	235520.0	244979.0
-2.4512634	-2.324459	-2.5701542	-2.0697155	-2.3653278	154726.0	154618.0	125367.0	281896.0	255967.0	248238.0
-3.1393166	-3.3582802	-2.986454	-3.2715225	-2.9517307	143776.0	155481.0	125788.0	70762.0	84536.0	110978.0
-19.75276	-19.745102	-20.058607	-19.87998	-19.850355	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
-19.75276	-19.745102	-20.058607	-19.87998	-19.850355	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
-0.23459053	-0.3371067	-0.60095406	-0.42586136	-0.29406548	158257.0	127498.0	147496.0	602047.0	606136.0	609873.0
-19.75276	-19.745102	-20.058607	-19.87998	-19.850355	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
-19.75276	-19.745102	-20.058607	-19.87998	-19.850355	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
-19.75276	-19.745102	-20.058607	-19.87998	-19.850355	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
-19.75276	-19.745102	-20.058607	-19.87998	-19.850355	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
-19.75276	-19.745102	-20.058607	-19.87998	-19.850355	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
-19.75276	-19.745102	-20.058607	-19.87998	-19.850355	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
-0.7336712	-0.9122715	-0.7976303	-0.9648609	-0.72397804	559775.0	537451.0	439370.0	379031.0	442921.0	531303.0
-0.45126534	-0.73822975	-0.24780464	-0.45417976	-0.27520943	885049.0	806349.0	705403.0	458473.0	499013.0	585554.0
-1.6298103	-1.6705952	-1.3447876	-1.3098583	-1.3053303	312530.0	316317.0	317978.0	183348.0	156342.0	168428.0
-19.75276	-19.745102	-20.058607	-19.87998	-19.850355	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
-1.464962	-1.5456219	-0.9685154	-0.8304157	-0.7861233	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
-19.75276	-19.745102	-20.058607	-19.87998	-19.850355	482679.0	457499.0	439352.0	351644.0	305019.0	312243.0
-19.75276	-19.745102	-20.058607	-19.87998	-19.850355	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
-19.75276	-19.745102	-20.058607	-19.87998	-19.850355	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
-19.75276	-19.745102	-20.058607	-19.87998	-19.850355	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
-1.7213993	-2.1338253	-1.5862331	-1.8947887	-1.6310768	259961.0	295981.0	233267.0	196215.0	203064.0	286542.0
-19.75276	-19.745102	-20.058607	-19.87998	-19.850355	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
-19.75276	-19.745102	-20.058607	-19.87998	-19.850355	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
-19.75276	-19.745102	-20.058607	-19.87998	-19.850355	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
-19.75276	-19.745102	-20.058607	-19.87998	-19.850355	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
-1.6996441	-0.6847439	-0.624033	-0.8373089	-0.7981205	313386.0	426416.0	373971.0	562688.0	732278.0	764797.0
-19.75276	-19.745102	-20.058607	-19.87998	-19.850355	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
-19.75276	-19.745102	-20.058607	-19.87998	-19.850355	144221.0	149246.0	133900.0	450265.0	433102.0	426438.0
-19.75276	-19.745102	-20.058607	-19.87998	-19.850355	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
-19.75276	-19.745102	-20.058607	-19.87998	-19.850355	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
-19.75276	-19.745102	-20.058607	-19.87998	-19.850355	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
-19.75276	-19.745102	-20.058607	-19.87998	-19.850355	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
-19.75276	-19.745102	-20.058607	-19.87998	-19.850355	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
-19.75276	-19.745102	-20.058607	-19.87998	-19.850355	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
-19.75276	-19.745102	-20.058607	-19.87998	-19.850355	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
-19.75276	-19.745102	-20.058607	-19.87998	-19.850355	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
-19.75276	-19.745102	-20.058607	-19.87998	-19.850355	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
-19.75276	-19.745102	-20.058607	-19.87998	-19.850355	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
-19.75276	-19.745102	-20.058607	-19.87998	-19.850355	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
-19.75276	-19.745102	-20.058607	-19.87998	-19.850355	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
-1.5260754	-1.5553837	-1.8363457	-1.6622772	-1.6427345	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
-19.75276	-19.745102	-20.058607	-19.87998	-19.850355	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
-0.65556526	-0.4619999	-1.0043793	-0.67497444	-0.71492195	466420.0	505175.0	525698.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
-1.418787	-1.6360168	-1.3905907	-1.3500271	-1.2193775	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
-19.75276	-19.745102	-20.058607	-19.87998	-19.850355	243896.0	238483.0	244297.0	166363.0	165411.0	166183.0
-19.75276	-19.745102	-20.058607	-19.87998	-19.850355	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
-19.75276	-19.745102	-20.058607	-19.87998	-19.850355	819800.0	714039.0	771333.0	564311.0	603895.0	668561.0
-19.75276	-19.745102	-20.058607	-19.87998	-19.850355	420348.0	422978.0	413784.0	158038.0	151435.0	159894.0

normalized_T 22_R2_2: Log 2	normalized_T 22_R2_3: Log 2	normalized_T 22_R3_1: Log 2	normalized_T 22_R3_2: Log 2	normalized_T 22_R3_3: Log 2	raw_6PP_R1 _1	raw_6PP_R1 _2	raw_6PP_R1 _3	raw_6PP_R2 _1	raw_6PP_R2 _2	raw_6PP_R2 _3
-19.75276	-19.745102	-20.058607	-19.87998	-19.850355	308700.0	250299.0	291757.0	323667.0	308755.0	308189.0
-19.75276	-19.745102	-20.058607	-19.87998	-19.850355	286392.0	254548.0	266828.0	286120.0	283236.0	232050.0
-19.75276	-19.745102	-20.058607	-19.87998	-19.850355	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
-19.75276	-19.745102	-20.058607	-19.87998	-19.850355	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
-19.75276	-19.745102	-20.058607	-19.87998	-19.850355	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0

raw_6PP_R3_1	raw_6PP_R3_2	raw_6PP_R3_3	raw_76A_R1_1	raw_76A_R1_2	raw_76A_R1_3	raw_76A_R2_1	raw_76A_R2_2	raw_76A_R2_3	raw_76A_R3_1	raw_76A_R3_2
302968.0	283658.0	272755.0	337792.0	337052.0	339703.0	298591.0	339189.0	316806.0	346491.0	337174.0
208929.0	197002.0	196911.0	359645.0	351350.0	350346.0	231214.0	244371.0	232105.0	350664.0	352466.0
65344.0	77731.0	85612.0	140335.0	142367.0	165420.0	113013.0	101271.0	126889.0	136440.0	90246.0
69000.0	75207.0	81752.0	166197.0	171119.0	197707.0	125849.0	111232.0	136145.0	141317.0	168134.0
119062.0	80664.0	82452.0	1210294.0	1199221.0	1301217.0	1489065.0	1803049.0	1389993.0	1405283.0	1587875.0
1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
553184.0	551487.0	508246.0	309969.0	285306.0	278696.0	958846.0	1010199.0	916604.0	255619.0	260425.0
1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
1.0	1.0	1.0	296466.0	399110.0	406770.0	264354.0	223673.0	170162.0	353350.0	405070.0
1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
588251.0	444647.0	407541.0	373810.0	510526.0	462285.0	527484.0	504264.0	463453.0	427775.0	556389.0
743541.0	567564.0	662745.0	686771.0	788609.0	674940.0	724127.0	893355.0	664782.0	723092.0	792144.0
362642.0	314913.0	304239.0	328590.0	311495.0	289208.0	282605.0	273239.0	299559.0	426494.0	394557.0
1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
1.0	1.0	1.0	627606.0	633902.0	630349.0	364606.0	378569.0	343361.0	622695.0	637740.0
547618.0	440850.0	513492.0	403323.0	422057.0	407421.0	396033.0	397713.0	401618.0	418438.0	402681.0
1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
334006.0	257489.0	226180.0	245652.0	306648.0	292546.0	291973.0	356236.0	194921.0	241919.0	285501.0
1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
259637.0	339237.0	512467.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
289942.0	289434.0	285800.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
1.0	1.0	1.0	808139.0	984570.0	810300.0	846746.0	1106939.0	868201.0	769875.0	894731.0
1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
506124.0	585945.0	631753.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
362091.0	363853.0	353517.0	206338.0	209454.0	218472.0	291463.0	303578.0	304114.0	277074.0	277287.0
1.0	1.0	1.0	286353.0	296594.0	299818.0	77601.0	82790.0	80404.0	304454.0	298658.0
892146.0	681572.0	654547.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
410520.0	386267.0	388774.0	261847.0	267686.0	255752.0	408496.0	430294.0	422839.0	357709.0	405710.0

raw_76A_R3_3	raw_BIO+6P_P_R1_1	raw_BIO+6P_P_R1_2	raw_BIO+6P_P_R1_3	raw_BIO+6P_P_R2_1	raw_BIO+6P_P_R2_2	raw_BIO+6P_P_R2_3	raw_BIO+6P_P_R3_1	raw_BIO+6P_P_R3_2	raw_BIO+6P_P_R3_3	raw_BIO+76_A_R1_1
2006504.0	3860864.0	3947860.0	3905042.0	9229747.0	9124338.0	9070163.0	1210720.0	1131623.0	1118202.0	4071804.0
3421726.0	4227868.0	4250385.0	4299373.0	6352143.0	6287188.0	6255250.0	2451033.0	2297271.0	2284055.0	4384537.0
223270.0	1455618.0	1429465.0	1445613.0	4748736.0	4934802.0	4742765.0	125503.0	138348.0	136957.0	1179984.0
684560.0	4535650.0	4985017.0	4532473.0	3259733.0	3221033.0	3171218.0	2864441.0	2626640.0	2822191.0	3814093.0
1209528.0	2521270.0	2369205.0	2404987.0	4173610.0	4461753.0	4220538.0	619373.0	744145.0	729931.0	3599386.0
3000416.0	2305219.0	2396073.0	2694278.0	2574908.0	2725743.0	2623764.0	2469058.0	2295856.0	2503725.0	2638619.0
1.0	2535985.0	2723257.0	2358710.0	3886977.0	4086450.0	3795739.0	1.0	975745.0	1161584.0	1.0
469446.0	387172.0	460193.0	460963.0	294058.0	295978.0	288253.0	560722.0	388539.0	513746.0	409794.0
1071374.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
1108647.0	660608.0	659647.0	770525.0	726487.0	1071791.0	728354.0	1155136.0	854160.0	961959.0	970536.0
991087.0	914897.0	867612.0	909676.0	666739.0	636157.0	627314.0	273964.0	247774.0	239617.0	507560.0
796448.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
394803.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
1130829.0	1395416.0	1413662.0	1410351.0	1507617.0	1502138.0	1515565.0	1214973.0	1131124.0	1127088.0	1420629.0
1339245.0	1251355.0	1493283.0	1284156.0	1120973.0	966468.0	1036765.0	1138521.0	1104993.0	1173698.0	620217.0
1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
1.0	463110.0	442702.0	449596.0	765512.0	818356.0	762297.0	119323.0	133662.0	137087.0	437920.0
1451847.0	1275049.0	1117880.0	1326062.0	1279775.0	1292819.0	1184254.0	1185883.0	1239597.0	1215695.0	1179239.0
1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
497293.0	726338.0	686033.0	692721.0	565845.0	548768.0	541069.0	518001.0	470268.0	467136.0	401844.0
1221746.0	1244850.0	1263576.0	1248491.0	1157288.0	1150994.0	1222687.0	1047090.0	1104250.0	1104244.0	1151517.0
658589.0	1189643.0	1315054.0	1347423.0	2662132.0	2487926.0	2605303.0	566805.0	547069.0	511744.0	313645.0
1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
1.0	212430.0	254114.0	270479.0	614243.0	548128.0	604067.0	62975.0	55092.0	52350.0	194409.0
1.0	215516.0	189503.0	178880.0	678835.0	741114.0	682187.0	11776.0	17061.0	17342.0	189862.0
75358.0	421409.0	568865.0	484387.0	510623.0	524366.0	521818.0	485816.0	457207.0	431936.0	654866.0
1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
738409.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
545481.0	572139.0	647762.0	548945.0	395686.0	405579.0	426221.0	443694.0	409217.0	434144.0	632144.0
480868.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
580912.0	534490.0	524887.0	521681.0	330763.0	324946.0	314623.0	231900.0	184969.0	178195.0	1.0
675512.0	831189.0	724591.0	864899.0	848320.0	851128.0	652443.0	660158.0	755079.0	741936.0	722329.0
729342.0	583712.0	514073.0	552304.0	478696.0	483475.0	479275.0	564477.0	587049.0	594604.0	558731.0
1248895.0	224269.0	223204.0	213353.0	382547.0	393379.0	374833.0	1166289.0	80470.0	77321.0	1996645.0
489481.0	667142.0	615910.0	619522.0	542044.0	751516.0	682637.0	438994.0	547370.0	391344.0	338487.0
601464.0	657885.0	664168.0	677510.0	488402.0	496298.0	495721.0	615638.0	627902.0	633687.0	825844.0
358504.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	218959.0
1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
1.0	384052.0	389004.0	388021.0	411277.0	406066.0	394978.0	130464.0	125992.0	130514.0	187869.0
76232.0	308780.0	253594.0	236736.0	451515.0	483901.0	456116.0	65554.0	86109.0	87689.0	305269.0
1.0	331620.0	343817.0	329583.0	788694.0	649620.0	785628.0	101454.0	87087.0	85043.0	1.0

raw_BIO+76A _R1_2	raw_BIO+76A _R1_3	raw_BIO+76A _R2_1	raw_BIO+76A _R2_2	raw_BIO+76A _R2_3	raw_BIO+76A _R3_1	raw_BIO+76A _R3_2	raw_BIO+76A _R3_3	raw_BIO+T22 +76A_R1_1	raw_BIO+T22 +76A_R1_2	raw_BIO+T22 +76A_R1_3
1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	457273.0	454569.0	457684.0
1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	654171.0	776931.0	667781.0

raw_BIO+T2 2+76A_R2_1	raw_BIO+T2 2+76A_R2_2	raw_BIO+T2 2+76A_R2_3	raw_BIO+T2 2+76A_R3_1	raw_BIO+T2 2+76A_R3_2	raw_BIO+T2 2+76A_R3_3	raw_BIO+T2 2_R1_1	raw_BIO+T2 2_R1_2	raw_BIO+T2 2_R1_3	raw_BIO+T2 2_R2_1	raw_BIO+T2 2_R2_2
3313235.0	3372339.0	3354225.0	7798462.0	7873753.0	7961309.0	3720311.0	3728825.0	3756101.0	5932699.0	6067370.0
4152253.0	4212818.0	4113646.0	5742572.0	5814251.0	5916467.0	4167869.0	4267978.0	4260725.0	5018976.0	5250754.0
412887.0	415274.0	409548.0	4121852.0	4095591.0	4193015.0	1078503.0	1069975.0	1229228.0	1934760.0	1921302.0
5246271.0	4908091.0	5476260.0	3333862.0	3124080.0	3367965.0	3311077.0	3310442.0	3271252.0	6661502.0	6891082.0
1758576.0	1766498.0	1749399.0	8183046.0	8202480.0	8348501.0	2863989.0	2911344.0	3317540.0	4651757.0	4495637.0
241473.0	270679.0	196075.0	204560.0	207058.0	214251.0	2205032.0	2254112.0	2200818.0	2616957.0	2393076.0
1646077.0	1608238.0	1816018.0	3179933.0	3860617.0	3856116.0	2241650.0	2242151.0	2196404.0	2090944.0	2111450.0
1364740.0	1371566.0	1127558.0	1463750.0	1474245.0	1474544.0	1101190.0	1193030.0	1155443.0	1512547.0	1743475.0
1235387.0	1266662.0	1328241.0	1546157.0	1558118.0	1566719.0	1125902.0	1136026.0	1114426.0	1668872.0	1600788.0
1864661.0	2085617.0	1981040.0	2294307.0	2269326.0	2193603.0	851976.0	971592.0	991181.0	1074420.0	1069384.0
1159542.0	1200253.0	1118728.0	502215.0	503207.0	504475.0	925851.0	965180.0	947215.0	826494.0	921921.0
885110.0	894114.0	965774.0	1112290.0	1091365.0	1094648.0	833807.0	836381.0	832042.0	1243751.0	1212920.0
1271852.0	1239274.0	1212083.0	987238.0	914899.0	952000.0	1027132.0	1101876.0	1039364.0	1015195.0	1117598.0
1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	863079.0	809106.0	955542.0	834185.0	1.0
530337.0	542580.0	561857.0	797528.0	817482.0	662451.0	615615.0	610789.0	609847.0	610169.0	600303.0
1178398.0	1012023.0	1180985.0	1336662.0	1357725.0	1153289.0	1225039.0	1210953.0	1189626.0	1156480.0	1164415.0
1201004.0	1251847.0	1350967.0	941389.0	783458.0	830651.0	1099211.0	979637.0	1089459.0	851700.0	863726.0
842786.0	882243.0	822634.0	647071.0	633402.0	643377.0	627517.0	653787.0	666033.0	637450.0	541509.0
254152.0	253978.0	250721.0	740686.0	748486.0	754502.0	338716.0	345546.0	397659.0	513224.0	486729.0
1014603.0	848063.0	828508.0	825218.0	786860.0	844932.0	612573.0	647916.0	508058.0	698142.0	944180.0
1050117.0	1103103.0	742616.0	712080.0	732766.0	723013.0	681058.0	755207.0	752698.0	695773.0	817260.0
1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	818278.0	789202.0	894825.0	1.0	1.0
477231.0	484468.0	437609.0	864826.0	891288.0	931565.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
774560.0	743257.0	733280.0	650749.0	611907.0	619844.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
840976.0	895307.0	705382.0	673890.0	601718.0	707290.0	415343.0	493228.0	457033.0	487483.0	833401.0
972624.0	821428.0	973054.0	2316386.0	2337864.0	2420647.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
1131103.0	1102139.0	1174073.0	1039556.0	1016394.0	1169948.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
174027.0	167268.0	186146.0	509188.0	499688.0	511783.0	251482.0	218459.0	220537.0	291182.0	314327.0
66970.0	90049.0	55157.0	432066.0	433757.0	452644.0	72478.0	116834.0	121553.0	273576.0	303737.0
726356.0	739373.0	709634.0	735767.0	732324.0	749169.0	534920.0	558204.0	547775.0	692238.0	743985.0
1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
750389.0	695345.0	705525.0	374506.0	377793.0	364732.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
535794.0	487931.0	541733.0	412553.0	442144.0	407056.0	581239.0	660840.0	651989.0	255421.0	326574.0
1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	350320.0	379535.0	392652.0	457188.0	482214.0
378554.0	374414.0	365049.0	341230.0	339520.0	330485.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
531996.0	554358.0	445773.0	450157.0	431048.0	387453.0	330128.0	318421.0	326636.0	360635.0	489042.0
518415.0	552375.0	608310.0	451830.0	458080.0	465938.0	420382.0	450747.0	459261.0	608382.0	645384.0
1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	226812.0	227187.0	231832.0	283296.0	285982.0
707695.0	739223.0	785597.0	585059.0	528111.0	486949.0	507881.0	434460.0	448430.0	540577.0	546299.0
566393.0	586821.0	595208.0	469943.0	454363.0	487199.0	612892.0	651427.0	647453.0	356964.0	363877.0
1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	427832.0	427917.0	428361.0	154187.0	154228.0
152149.0	170133.0	143249.0	519243.0	498854.0	507835.0	93122.0	121004.0	101068.0	303338.0	261615.0
1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	179672.0	255942.0	131227.0	116178.0	174855.0

raw_BIO+T22 +76A_R2_1	raw_BIO+T22 +76A_R2_2	raw_BIO+T22 +76A_R2_3	raw_BIO+T22 +76A_R3_1	raw_BIO+T22 +76A_R3_2	raw_BIO+T22 +76A_R3_3	raw_BIO+T22 _R1_1	raw_BIO+T22 _R1_2	raw_BIO+T22 _R1_3	raw_BIO+T22 _R2_1	raw_BIO+T22 _R2_2
576086.0	573747.0	556745.0	466460.0	470342.0	469673.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
434560.0	519632.0	460019.0	434696.0	426871.0	407366.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0

raw_BIO+T2 2_R2_3	raw_BIO+T2 2_R3_1	raw_BIO+T2 2_R3_2	raw_BIO+T2 2_R3_3	raw_BIO_R1 _1	raw_BIO_R1 _2	raw_BIO_R1 _3	raw_BIO_R2 _1	raw_BIO_R2 _2	raw_BIO_R2 _3	raw_BIO_R3 _1
6010915.0	4696031.0	4795385.0	4863131.0	4502929.0	4652855.0	4518775.0	9455431.0	9465897.0	9396688.0	2954278.0
5211697.0	4563071.0	4731428.0	4756539.0	4370600.0	4499343.0	4406626.0	6048249.0	5999208.0	6026141.0	3827098.0
1951367.0	1067562.0	1084175.0	1099977.0	2309951.0	2411251.0	2415449.0	6033629.0	6254169.0	5915566.0	274759.0
6684478.0	5207117.0	5264400.0	5311577.0	3457132.0	3535462.0	3395065.0	5477491.0	5490059.0	5446667.0	2613005.0
4652727.0	3110949.0	3064127.0	3115099.0	4997625.0	5169710.0	5334597.0	1.0585531E7	1.1100089E7	1.0395055E7	1380688.0
2638400.0	2395824.0	2331645.0	2491146.0	273262.0	271708.0	189733.0	241958.0	256729.0	173868.0	241682.0
2084511.0	1955390.0	2099572.0	2106312.0	2620350.0	2321331.0	2468853.0	3436734.0	3465051.0	3392735.0	1615712.0
1486302.0	1674854.0	1741507.0	1805199.0	895932.0	967344.0	876170.0	1134767.0	1284470.0	1232712.0	1487727.0
1652069.0	1119264.0	1182701.0	1140917.0	1205762.0	1094674.0	1214228.0	1295834.0	1294658.0	1296855.0	1718196.0
1042662.0	1009701.0	927267.0	1005615.0	1519679.0	1705464.0	1682413.0	1802105.0	2134525.0	2105292.0	2854354.0
821984.0	1149073.0	1222142.0	1218045.0	1119721.0	1227756.0	1143131.0	653707.0	666138.0	658104.0	594881.0
1240938.0	727593.0	761413.0	759774.0	898865.0	816883.0	892284.0	976574.0	958092.0	970451.0	1269608.0
1024568.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	980727.0	1079086.0	1013239.0	907041.0	995476.0	904574.0	1167790.0
1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	523586.0	514669.0	528729.0	1075298.0	1070520.0	1130776.0	567370.0
1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1863079.0	726891.0	725873.0	998861.0	872924.0	883173.0	900724.0
611236.0	502173.0	696199.0	720022.0	964556.0	942897.0	970938.0	969399.0	958896.0	969152.0	608081.0
1174227.0	1062474.0	1077924.0	1092264.0	1105298.0	1127900.0	1098320.0	1345547.0	1321802.0	1334779.0	678265.0
831076.0	1044674.0	1124802.0	1091208.0	882280.0	967890.0	988047.0	758111.0	724930.0	745925.0	901595.0
645271.0	767947.0	760888.0	819000.0	595072.0	532750.0	628400.0	510601.0	629951.0	615502.0	722756.0
511527.0	363745.0	381157.0	379658.0	492687.0	500631.0	527571.0	817632.0	863340.0	808843.0	211085.0
713644.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	607517.0	720103.0	651408.0	656023.0	772048.0	565694.0	752473.0
751488.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	651174.0	807555.0	709027.0	637991.0	757294.0	677682.0	808745.0
1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	824606.0	237651.0	209368.0	520153.0	439446.0	435529.0	1.0
1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	537792.0	618072.0	535251.0	716663.0	899128.0	847889.0	278294.0
1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	629864.0	630831.0	616376.0	934519.0	635630.0	890163.0	820913.0
450382.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	369642.0	634068.0	471108.0	387780.0	324481.0	499191.0	515874.0
1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1771631.0	1940718.0	1600104.0	3013571.0	2728707.0	2759215.0	520475.0
1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	778614.0	801475.0	775210.0	1007375.0	1016675.0	873826.0	67633.0
1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	662217.0	689142.0	566513.0	865446.0	1044607.0	961340.0	1300189.0
318225.0	245859.0	220809.0	235700.0	392030.0	403773.0	356719.0	702111.0	620526.0	620525.0	99146.0
265349.0	205651.0	237441.0	232290.0	204008.0	250256.0	248621.0	567409.0	678879.0	676168.0	32956.0
720777.0	711767.0	722802.0	762231.0	350912.0	407683.0	349819.0	458536.0	457726.0	455452.0	599886.0
1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	418286.0	364058.0	419043.0	512756.0	508456.0	509013.0	540346.0
1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	549100.0	545650.0	514645.0	568188.0	541929.0	555882.0	599966.0
290330.0	389177.0	452568.0	482744.0	502271.0	464084.0	538054.0	431711.0	469423.0	501438.0	290704.0
479470.0	290963.0	294502.0	297262.0	520226.0	556998.0	538115.0	340050.0	336281.0	338284.0	217170.0
1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	362805.0	135005.0	120430.0	584083.0	549883.0	557118.0	532368.0
367018.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	307930.0	363191.0	362462.0	369631.0	411384.0	374900.0	402504.0
619432.0	548871.0	555600.0	565806.0	435391.0	467626.0	443895.0	481508.0	490292.0	491205.0	544645.0
305667.0	161167.0	167724.0	167539.0	285470.0	307371.0	282793.0	476553.0	475346.0	477959.0	161598.0
546924.0	577497.0	615681.0	606210.0	444495.0	551796.0	460839.0	514709.0	481127.0	497778.0	468964.0
360241.0	555257.0	559318.0	579393.0	478896.0	496491.0	474439.0	444680.0	434594.0	439288.0	392150.0
1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	235113.0	237462.0	232705.0	346277.0	243424.0	333481.0	361512.0
1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	148222.0	130259.0	112619.0	101963.0	85601.0	169211.0	36338.0
155461.0	271643.0	253433.0	249831.0	306984.0	314257.0	304510.0	149931.0	154918.0	155501.0	410658.0
293245.0	299100.0	322318.0	323871.0	126442.0	90614.0	142144.0	370969.0	416570.0	429755.0	155791.0
79230.0	118271.0	137532.0	139636.0	233218.0	242923.0	108092.0	102319.0	77746.0	348294.0	16224.0

raw_BIO_R3_2	raw_BIO_R3_3	raw_C_R1_1	raw_C_R1_2	raw_C_R1_3	raw_C_R2_1	raw_C_R2_2	raw_C_R2_3	raw_C_R3_1	raw_C_R3_2	raw_C_R3_3
333641.0	334363.0	236943.0	259400.0	266812.0	386006.0	374381.0	369450.0	368573.0	394796.0	396668.0
322457.0	308263.0	338142.0	392750.0	405145.0	388838.0	393730.0	387023.0	286357.0	300403.0	307224.0
79446.0	105080.0	148475.0	300034.0	322279.0	202181.0	98855.0	88936.0	116434.0	154231.0	153453.0
108891.0	127166.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
1.0	1.0	1271044.0	1526029.0	1504402.0	1482036.0	1526956.0	1393813.0	1376453.0	1492970.0	1792969.0
1.0	1.0	1476610.0	1840093.0	1932485.0	4177691.0	4058041.0	4197609.0	4910673.0	4884164.0	4855967.0
1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
1.0	1.0	293241.0	291617.0	306759.0	528159.0	601137.0	584096.0	856869.0	844667.0	866852.0
1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	680892.0	702938.0	750485.0	874326.0	812130.0	787846.0
1.0	1.0	317043.0	228028.0	225941.0	294382.0	160631.0	325646.0	280754.0	245692.0	199397.0
1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
1.0	1.0	521400.0	710552.0	676178.0	627465.0	662712.0	507305.0	501355.0	506651.0	575264.0
1.0	1.0	491646.0	702374.0	785835.0	874366.0	800089.0	716900.0	698159.0	842854.0	985116.0
1.0	1.0	310076.0	326931.0	342754.0	263413.0	279089.0	273552.0	317968.0	309321.0	344544.0
1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
1.0	1.0	460272.0	516900.0	540533.0	403141.0	401701.0	380871.0	421830.0	439794.0	445858.0
1.0	1.0	312846.0	384761.0	403444.0	453408.0	451039.0	436981.0	394573.0	396376.0	398680.0
1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
1.0	1.0	250616.0	340043.0	310739.0	312459.0	239243.0	233690.0	205892.0	238686.0	304566.0
1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
1.0	1.0	662721.0	632436.0	852847.0	1018877.0	802376.0	668728.0	777401.0	878902.0	986630.0
1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
1.0	1.0	409406.0	454390.0	477206.0	383204.0	380339.0	372125.0	517712.0	533801.0	540067.0
1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
1.0	1.0	213932.0	241946.0	252236.0	232157.0	226813.0	214342.0	289900.0	303979.0	314711.0
1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
1.0	1.0	182411.0	213063.0	223080.0	595777.0	615894.0	625462.0	256079.0	259749.0	260390.0

raw_T22+76 A_R1_1	raw_T22+76 A_R1_2	raw_T22+76 A_R1_3	raw_T22+76 A_R2_1	raw_T22+76 A_R2_2	raw_T22+76 A_R2_3	raw_T22+76 A_R3_1	raw_T22+76 A_R3_2	raw_T22+76 A_R3_3	raw_T22_R1 _1	raw_T22_R1 _2
1.2577662E7	1.2627363E7	1.2624486E7	1.0750431E7	1.0696785E7	1.0553861E7	6279435.0	6472954.0	6302418.0	1264257.0	1281288.0
7340238.0	7332506.0	7261744.0	6972430.0	7018659.0	6698976.0	5401539.0	5750108.0	5464498.0	2600482.0	2545384.0
1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	149263.0	143180.0
2623389.0	2624355.0	2605788.0	4677477.0	4636956.0	4594003.0	3397412.0	3818793.0	3741384.0	4989994.0	4893148.0
1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	909281.0	884451.0
2438814.0	2407318.0	2575003.0	2814950.0	2852312.0	2817530.0	2567104.0	3011815.0	2416725.0	2632174.0	2715130.0
1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1606286.0	1650387.0
1291753.0	1378184.0	1365652.0	1700456.0	1790680.0	1522919.0	1483774.0	1672515.0	1285621.0	1274269.0	1040304.0
1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	701660.0	861281.0
755114.0	699079.0	690223.0	923289.0	867438.0	849575.0	742813.0	872930.0	920904.0	1029271.0	1011910.0
1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1062359.0	962578.0
1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	483237.0	593877.0
1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1220030.0	1034099.0
1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
1141240.0	710383.0	1127781.0	723040.0	721090.0	740728.0	669665.0	675754.0	732141.0	280401.0	293611.0
818074.0	797341.0	799589.0	892869.0	857264.0	831692.0	689767.0	712117.0	707087.0	1576610.0	1580834.0
1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	540205.0	541392.0
1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	523312.0	530481.0
871889.0	852853.0	870557.0	828892.0	881226.0	839216.0	564204.0	570227.0	549443.0	145826.0	137965.0
963334.0	957437.0	1044503.0	1160799.0	1165491.0	1000191.0	951671.0	1092604.0	1029939.0	776114.0	691628.0
1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	775074.0	986446.0
1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	986782.0	807605.0
1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
370345.0	328289.0	335644.0	690572.0	650095.0	519079.0	600587.0	505546.0	643597.0	1.0	1.0
628117.0	792232.0	782017.0	911809.0	930169.0	742472.0	787339.0	1067682.0	696026.0	678040.0	624388.0
3351709.0	3432218.0	2902126.0	2360347.0	2827956.0	2834230.0	1448996.0	1473696.0	1703336.0	518627.0	666028.0
733971.0	956530.0	972822.0	719284.0	703419.0	690176.0	328336.0	353445.0	335652.0	1.0	1.0
1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
849292.0	823696.0	788459.0	514493.0	522179.0	552398.0	281165.0	270163.0	393274.0	57819.0	59961.0
1075775.0	1165223.0	1196870.0	957453.0	955517.0	838090.0	481129.0	552077.0	293081.0	17241.0	7802.0
520586.0	567702.0	555353.0	703810.0	624935.0	531327.0	577884.0	766171.0	475841.0	201437.0	218674.0
1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
317052.0	309935.0	317658.0	682727.0	659051.0	625443.0	678142.0	718279.0	695970.0	488054.0	481996.0
482498.0	199663.0	178551.0	451766.0	220837.0	225859.0	462377.0	297073.0	247404.0	1389801.0	1413899.0
404619.0	429377.0	412388.0	285688.0	284934.0	273190.0	520672.0	571428.0	522477.0	375582.0	364062.0
1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	424068.0	410130.0
1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	589457.0	553608.0
3895934.0	3754915.0	3960817.0	3141018.0	3133650.0	3046616.0	2430962.0	2525750.0	2629041.0	154969.0	149594.0
1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	365062.0	366856.0
1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	324207.0	308192.0
577216.0	582763.0	567465.0	488557.0	489227.0	491461.0	258998.0	269871.0	284396.0	1.0	1.0
1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	312390.0	314813.0
331903.0	325858.0	346989.0	473583.0	446107.0	419774.0	279872.0	260238.0	291934.0	55604.0	64255.0
356089.0	455934.0	597656.0	437329.0	237081.0	450265.0	105869.0	139413.0	89778.0	1.0	1.0

raw_T22_R1 _3	raw_T22_R2 _1	raw_T22_R2 _2	raw_T22_R2 _3	raw_T22_R3 _1	raw_T22_R3 _2	raw_T22_R3 _3	super.FC ([6 PP] vs [CTR L])	super.Log F C ([6PP] vs [CTRL])	super.FC (ab s) ([6PP] vs [CTRL])	super.FC ([7 6A] vs [CTRL])
1273076.0	5646997.0	5747026.0	5706906.0	7180073.0	7159078.0	7057434.0				
2618123.0	5023652.0	5162423.0	5012176.0	6337964.0	6113049.0	6159500.0				
151134.0	1970745.0	2025233.0	1945885.0	1823647.0	1840178.0	1921626.0				
5004839.0	2946685.0	2957711.0	2956493.0	5816549.0	5841797.0	5786909.0				
909450.0	4709317.0	4801762.0	4577090.0	4523950.0	4584678.0	4821085.0				
2480660.0	2921856.0	3480460.0	3226290.0	3248597.0	2899364.0	2936956.0				
1579237.0	3335416.0	3329060.0	3407184.0	2492248.0	2505249.0	2473573.0				
1355567.0	1493478.0	1313859.0	1262657.0	1514431.0	1401966.0	1487472.0				
759185.0	1510493.0	1431663.0	1587989.0	1652874.0	1861255.0	1728501.0				
1021616.0	1142557.0	1227555.0	884103.0	874872.0	1010035.0	944986.0				
1010718.0	788634.0	818754.0	759919.0	1225796.0	1130951.0	1143725.0				
531260.0	1095562.0	1036696.0	1156781.0	1181909.0	1362434.0	1252560.0				
1110443.0	1098886.0	1097364.0	1107713.0	1288248.0	966944.0	1150381.0				
1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	-1.2872281	-0.3642677	1.2872281	-1.3700604
1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0				
282996.0	898654.0	883433.0	897228.0	864015.0	888817.0	845539.0				
1599033.0	886160.0	874752.0	888316.0	712761.0	699967.0	688240.0				
563379.0	389251.0	381347.0	367576.0	318775.0	305685.0	310445.0				
694400.0	524196.0	509829.0	567538.0	754263.0	579125.0	532443.0				
145625.0	501109.0	505127.0	480717.0	503124.0	501643.0	531418.0				
747146.0	702612.0	829048.0	823901.0	1049900.0	797807.0	982728.0				
1053549.0	752662.0	869879.0	595609.0	1114366.0	783578.0	870269.0				
604043.0	623181.0	693259.0	699223.0	1.0	1.0	1.0				
1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	-1.2415491	-0.31214142	1.2415491	-2.326867
1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0				
643212.0	871536.0	908060.0	730983.0	1092049.0	649603.0	945262.0				
551352.0	1792707.0	1759058.0	1775606.0	1385449.0	1495075.0	1329634.0				
1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0				
1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0				
59003.0	341123.0	323308.0	349927.0	319302.0	396434.0	303208.0				
9861.0	202715.0	255823.0	196461.0	507457.0	375328.0	513384.0				
198836.0	176372.0	143073.0	186700.0	195777.0	234388.0	197761.0				
1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0				
500839.0	398083.0	394413.0	395601.0	807330.0	806329.0	780010.0				
1296374.0	714518.0	804175.0	825974.0	817669.0	807943.0	891679.0				
380270.0	243488.0	251209.0	247339.0	634855.0	634070.0	649224.0				
408819.0	267009.0	268306.0	267115.0	633859.0	585798.0	592728.0				
1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0				
606382.0	470993.0	492367.0	462617.0	643475.0	610187.0	636184.0				
158217.0	335035.0	346329.0	352606.0	345138.0	346578.0	373700.0				
384268.0	418824.0	398043.0	478051.0	538513.0	544161.0	444969.0	3303188.8	21.655428	3303188.8	2684024.8
1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0				
324756.0	216545.0	208673.0	199490.0	416266.0	375903.0	331303.0				
1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0				
316361.0	261013.0	247922.0	253178.0	418843.0	413309.0	399066.0				
53076.0	304098.0	284340.0	253544.0	280726.0	257299.0	260774.0				
1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0				

raw_T22_R1 _3	raw_T22_R2 _1	raw_T22_R2 _2	raw_T22_R2 _3	raw_T22_R3 _1	raw_T22_R3 _2	raw_T22_R3 _3	super.FC ([6 PP] vs [CTR L])	super.Log F C ([6PP] vs [CTRL])	super.FC (ab s) ([6PP] vs [CTRL])	super.FC ([7 6A] vs [CTRL])
1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0				
471678.0	220974.0	227953.0	213084.0	345975.0	331245.0	338015.0				
147071.0	77001.0	93758.0	108479.0	218149.0	148729.0	147036.0				
212819.0	170894.0	161536.0	175443.0	183886.0	229839.0	183450.0				
106831.0	87397.0	100264.0	85689.0	137794.0	99918.0	122178.0				
1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0				
1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0				
211598.0	732849.0	750852.0	695647.0	720008.0	718246.0	770956.0				
1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0				
1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0				
1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	-824691.94	-19.653496	824691.94	-1.6783471
1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	12.501879	3.644073	12.501879	1.3037983
1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0				
1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0				
378415.0	455811.0	531271.0	466925.0	628249.0	494331.0	572286.0				
663675.0	730293.0	646143.0	526791.0	919699.0	704285.0	781099.0				
316039.0	311717.0	285464.0	276038.0	429953.0	389192.0	382480.0				
1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0				
414895.0	303978.0	320019.0	301016.0	558072.0	542613.0	548158.0				
1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0				
1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0				
1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0				
1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0				
244662.0	233826.0	267905.0	200227.0	363696.0	259467.0	305175.0				
1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0				
1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0				
1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0				
1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0				
274629.0	413859.0	271975.0	546688.0	708582.0	540027.0	543618.0				
1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0				
1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0				
1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0				
1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0				
1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0				
1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0				
1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0				
1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0				
1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0				
1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0				
1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0				
643416.0	338402.0	306746.0	298986.0	305807.0	304842.0	302719.0				
1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0				
476940.0	613466.0	560826.0	637958.0	544370.0	604342.0	575890.0				
343816.0	310749.0	330427.0	282734.0	416517.0	378505.0	405960.0				
1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0				
1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0				
1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0				
1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0				

raw_T22_R1_3	raw_T22_R2_1	raw_T22_R2_2	raw_T22_R2_3	raw_T22_R3_1	raw_T22_R3_2	raw_T22_R3_3	super.FC ([6P P] vs [CTRL])	super.Log FC ([6PP] vs [CTRL])	super.FC (abs) ([6PP] vs [CTRL])	super.FC ([76 A] vs [CTRL])
1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0				
1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0				
1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0				
1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0				
1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0				

super.FC (abs) ([T22+76A] vs [CTRL])

3356787.8

1.4316509

8767152.0

super.FC (abs) ([T22+76A] vs [CTRL])

1110060.4
8.193661

super.FC (abs) ([T22+76A] vs [CTRL])